

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process

D3.3 REPORT ON LCA FOR ACTIVITIES DEVELOPED IN ORDER TO IMPROVE SOIL HEALTH IN LHs

FiBL

Universidade de Vigo

Report on LCA for activities developed in order to improve soil health in LHs

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Executive Summary

Purpose

This deliverable is a report on the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of activities carried out to create a framework for investment in soil conservation and recovery by developing an economic valuation system for the ecosystem services provided by healthy soil. The InBestSoil project will generate data, evidence, tools, and models to assess how investment in soil health can contribute to the transition toward a long-term resilient and sustainable use of soil through nine case studies: seven Lighthouses (LHs) and two Living Labs (LLs). An LCA will be conducted for each case study using the SIMAPRO® software. The results obtained will highlight the environmental implications of the interventions.

Intended audience

The intended audience and potential readers for this deliverable have been defined considering the final objective of the project. This document is relevant for decision-makers in land-use planning, environmental managers, researchers, land managers, and industry stakeholders seeking to define environmental practices aimed at improving soil health. The project will provide insights for policymakers at local, national, and EU levels, helping to align soil management strategies with climate and biodiversity goals. Additionally, it supports scientists and practitioners in designing and assessing interventions that enhance soil health and ecosystem services.

Description of the main activities

In this project, the LCA is used to evaluate the environmental impact of various soil management interventions in different cases studies. Each case of study is based on the soil type (agricultural, urban, forestry or industrial) and the biogeographic region in Europe (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic and Mediterranean).

LCA serves as a powerful tool for guiding policy interventions toward environmentally sustainable soil management practices. Key policy challenges include minimizing the environmental impact of mineral fertilization and optimizing land-use systems by improving the effectiveness of sustainable management strategies across different soil types and uses.

The soil management practices implemented within each InBestSoil case study are analysed using Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). These practices include conventional, biodynamic, and regenerative systems; organic farming; conventional and reduced tillage; direct seeding; cover cropping; application of organic amendments; composting; mulching; reforestation; soil remediation techniques; and rotational grazing, among others.

Key results

The LCA modelling was carried out using SimaPro software, a professional tool for assessing the environmental impacts of products, processes, and activities.

The most important results of this deliverable are important findings regarding the environmental performance of soil management practices:

- **Key soil management practices and impacts:** high-impact activities and their environmental effects on soil health are identified.
- **Environmental benefits of sustainable practices:** certain soil management approaches reduce emissions and improve resource efficiency.
- **LCA informs decision-making:** assessment highlights high-impact processes and supports context-specific sustainable interventions.

Research and practice implications

These findings emphasize the importance of integrating LCA into soil management decision-making to ensure environmentally sustainable practices. The obtained results suggest that soil management strategies should prioritize:

- Minimizing trade-offs between soil restoration and energy consumption, optimizing mechanization and input use.
- Adapting soil interventions to regional conditions, ensuring their effectiveness across different biogeographic zones.

For land managers, these insights provide science-based recommendations to refine best management practices while maximizing soil health benefits. For researchers, the findings support further exploration into soil interactions, biodiversity impacts, and circular economy approaches in soil management.

Policy implications

One of the main goals of the InBestSoil project is to contribute to the EU Soil Strategy for 2030. InBestSoil is clearly related since promoting public and private investment in soil health, mitigate climate change, reduce pollution and nutrient losses, minimise desertification risk, improve soil biodiversity while generation fair economic returns. Project findings are related with the EU Mission Soil objectives, reinforcing the need for policy frameworks that:

- Promote regenerative agriculture and nature-based solutions to enhance carbon sequestration and soil fertility.
- Incentivize sustainable land management practices through subsidies, carbon credits, and eco-certification programs.
- Integrate LCA in soil health policies, ensuring that environmental impacts are systematically assessed before large-scale implementation.

At the EU level, these insights support the European Green Deal and the Soil Strategy for 2030, helping decision-makers craft policies that balance soil health, climate action, and sustainable land use.

Conclusion

The LCA of soil interventions assesses the contribution of various soil management practices across different impact categories (global warming, stratospheric ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, freshwater and marine eutrophication, ecotoxicity, fossil resource scarcity, etc.). It examines the potential of these interventions to enhance soil quality while minimizing environmental impact.

This deliverable supports evidence-based decision-making, offering valuable insights for land managers, policymakers, and researchers to enhance soil health and climate resilience while minimizing environmental burdens.

1. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

Life Cycle Assessment has become an invaluable tool for quantifying the environmental and potential impacts of a product throughout its life cycle, from raw material acquisition to production, use, and end-of-life treatment (recycling and final disposal). Life cycle studies can be conducted in various scopes: cradle to gate (raw materials to the factory or farm gate), gate to gate (focusing only on manufacturing or transformation processes), or cradle to grave (raw materials to disposal) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Stages of the Life Cycle Assessment, ranging from raw material extraction to final disposal.

The role of LCA, as defined in ISO 14040, is to clarify the environmental aspects of a product or service throughout its life cycle. LCA can help identify life cycle stages that need improvement from an environmental performance perspective and assist decision-makers in industry, government, or other organizations in designing systems or determining strategies. At this point, relevant parameters and indicators of environmental performance can also be specified. LCA results can be used to market products or services through eco-labels or environmental product declarations.

1.1. Methodology description

According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), particularly ISO 14040:2006 and ISO 14044:2006, the Life Cycle Analysis method is structured into four iterative phases (Figure 2): goal and scope definition, inventory analysis, impact assessment, and interpretation.

Figure 2. Framework of Life Cycle Assessment according to ISO 14040.

Goal and scope definition

Goal and scope definition is the first phase of an LCA study and involves establishing all general decisions used to conduct the analysis. This phase defines the analysis's objective, the target audience, the product, process or service being investigated, the functional unit, system boundaries, assumptions and constraints of the study, data requirements, and the impact assessment method adopted. The functional unit and system boundaries are two key parameters defined in this phase.

The **functional unit** is the reference to which input and output data related to the system under investigation are normalized. It must be clearly defined and measurable, allowing comparison between different systems. On the other hand, **system boundaries** define which life cycle stages and processes are included in the study and which are excluded from the analysis, known as "cut-off".

In this study, the functional unit is defined as 1 hectare of managed soil. All data related to energy consumption, transportation, inputs, and processes are normalized to this area, enabling a direct comparison of environmental impacts across different soil management scenarios.

The system boundaries are defined using the **cradle-to-farm gate** approach. The environmental assessment for the soil remediation process includes the extraction of raw materials (such as fossil fuels and minerals), manufacturing processes (remediation-related materials), usage (diesel consumption, equipment operation, and emissions from machinery use), maintenance (upkeep of remediation equipment and soil amendments), and the final disposal of machinery and materials at the end of their service life.

Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)

The Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) phase is the most extensive phase of an LCA study. It involves defining all **material and energy flows** associated with each process included within the system boundaries.

In this study, the **LCI for soil management practices** integrates both **primary** and **secondary** data sources.

- **Primary data** is obtained through field assessments and surveys of land management practitioners, including operational hours ($\text{h}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$), fuel consumption ($\text{L}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), application rates of raw materials ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$), and biomass production outputs ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$).

- **Secondary data** is sourced from the **Ecoinvent® database 3.10v**, covering the production processes of essential inputs such as raw materials, fuel, and machinery.

The estimation of machinery usage for each land management activity (kg machinery·h⁻¹) is based on the recorded useful lifespan of equipment in **Ecoinvent® database 3.10v**, supplemented with weight and operational time data gathered from field surveys. This comprehensive approach ensures a robust assessment of the environmental impacts and resource efficiency of soil health improvement strategies.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

In this phase, the potential environmental effects associated with the inputs and outputs identified in the inventory are evaluated. Models and methods are used to **quantify the impact in categories** such as climate change, resource depletion, toxicity, and others.

The environmental analysis of the soil management systems involved in this study will be assessed using the **ReCiPe 2016 Hierarchist Midpoint method**. This approach condenses extensive life cycle inventory data into a set of indicator scores, providing a comparative assessment of the relative severity of different environmental impact categories. To model the systems under evaluation, **SimaPro 9.6** software will be used. The ReCiPe 2016 database method at the midpoint level considers 18 environmental impact categories, which are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. The 18 environmental impacts considered in the ReCiPe 2016 database method at the midpoint level.

Impact Category	Units
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC ₁₁ eq
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NO _x eq
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM _{2.5} eq
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NO _x eq
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB
Land use	m ² a crop eq
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq
Water consumption	m ³

- **Global warming** quantifies CO₂ emissions contributing to temperature changes and weather disruptions. Human activities, especially fossil fuel consumption, have significantly increased greenhouse gases like CO₂, CH₄, and NO_x.

- **Stratospheric ozone depletion** refers to the thinning of the ozone layer due to emissions of CFCs, halons, and other chemicals. This results in higher UV radiation exposure, increasing skin cancer and cataract risks while harming ecosystems, agriculture, and marine life.
- **Ionizing radiation** assesses human and environmental exposure to radioactive emissions from nuclear energy, medical treatments, and industry. Prolonged exposure can lead to cancer, genetic mutations, and long-term soil and water contamination.
- **Ozone formation (human health)** measures ground-level ozone pollution from NO_x and VOC emissions reacting with sunlight. It contributes to smog and causes respiratory issues, lung inflammation, and cardiovascular diseases.
- **Fine particulate matter formation** refers to the emission of PM_{2.5} particles from combustion, industry, and traffic. These particles penetrate the lungs and bloodstream, increasing respiratory and cardiovascular diseases while reducing air quality.
- **Ozone formation (terrestrial ecosystems)** evaluates how ground-level ozone harms vegetation, reducing photosynthesis, plant resistance, and crop yields. It disrupts species interactions and biodiversity.
- **Acid deposition** results from atmospheric pollutants like NH₃, NO_x, and SO_x, leading to acid rain. It damages ecosystems, affecting soil fertility, water quality, and forest health.
- **Eutrophication** occurs when excess nutrients, mainly nitrogen and phosphorus, lead to uncontrolled algal growth in water bodies. This process depletes oxygen, causing anoxic conditions, fish deaths, and ecosystem imbalances.
- **Human toxicity and ecotoxicity** account for chemical persistence in the environment, accumulation in the food chain, and harmful effects on human health and ecosystems.
- **Land use** evaluates the impact of human activities such as agriculture and urbanization on biodiversity, soil quality, and water cycles. Poor land management leads to habitat destruction and environmental degradation.
- **Fossil resource scarcity** refers to the depletion of non-renewable fossil fuels (oil, coal, natural gas). Their consumption outpaces their natural regeneration, impacting long-term energy availability and sustainability.

Interpretation of results

The final phase of an LCA study involves **discussing the results** obtained from the inventory analysis and impact assessment phases. Additionally, it includes recommendations, limitations, and conclusions related to the analysis.

1.2. Uncertainty framework

LCA results are inherently subject to uncertainty arising from the complexity of environmental systems, the limitations of inventory data, and the methodological choices involved in impact assessment. In accordance with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044, two types of uncertainty are identified and addressed in this study.

- **Model uncertainty** arises from the characterisation factors embedded in the ReCiPe 2016 Hierarchist Midpoint method, which translate inventory flows into impact scores. This type of uncertainty is particularly significant for the ecotoxicity categories, terrestrial ecotoxicity (TET) and human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT), where characterisation factors for pesticides and heavy metals are known to carry confidence intervals spanning one to two orders of magnitude. Consequently, while these impact categories are informative for relative comparisons between management systems at the same site, their absolute values should be interpreted with caution.
- **Parameter uncertainty** relates to the quality and representativeness of the input data used to build the life cycle inventory. Primary data (including fuel consumption, application rates of fertilisers and amendments, and machinery working hours) were collected through field surveys and interviews with land managers. These data may carry estimation errors and do not capture year-to-year operational variability. Secondary data drawn from the Ecoinvent 3.10v database represent average European production processes and may not fully reflect the specific technologies, supply chains, or energy mixes of each case study site.

2. Environmental impact assessment of soil interventions

This report presents an environmental impact assessment of soil interventions within the InBestSoil project, which includes nine case studies: seven Lighthouses (LH) and two Living Labs (LL) at different stages of maturity. These case studies cover agriculture, forestry, urban, and industrial land uses across four biogeographical regions in Europe: Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, and Mediterranean. Following the definitions given by the **Implementation Plan for the Soil Mission**, we consider a LH as a place for demonstration of long-term solutions, that are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement, and a LL as the collaboration among some research and innovation ecosystems, which involve regional stakeholders in systemic research and codesign, to jointly improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health.

An environmental impact assessment of the soil interventions across the case studies is conducted. The assessment is based on a **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) approach, following ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 principles**, and aims to identify the main processes and activities driving environmental impacts throughout the implementation of the soil management practices.

Given the diversity of interventions and data availability across case studies, the assessment focuses on the operational stages directly linked to the implementation of the soil interventions, including material preparation, transport, and field application.

For a comprehensive LCA of soil management practices, direct field emissions (CO₂, CH₄, N₂O) and changes in soil carbon stocks should ideally be included, as these can represent significant components of the total environmental impact, particularly for greenhouse gas emissions. Within the InBestSoil project, field samples were collected across different case studies to measure these emissions. However, at the time of preparing this deliverable, only limited emission data were available from field measurements. Including incomplete or non-representative emission data would introduce significant variability and inconsistency across case studies, making comparisons unreliable and potentially misleading. Therefore, to ensure methodological consistency and comparability across all case studies, this LCA focuses exclusively on the environmental impacts associated with management practices (production and application of inputs, machinery operations, etc.), without accounting for direct soil emissions or carbon stock changes. This approach allows for a standardized assessment of the operational interventions while acknowledging that the results represent a partial environmental profile.

The results of this environmental impact assessment are intended to support the comparison of different soil management strategies, identify key impact hotspots, and inform decision-making regarding the environmental performance and sustainability of soil management practices within the InBestSoil framework.

Figure 3. Overview of the nine InBestSoil case studies: Lighthouses (1-7) and Living Labs (8-9).

2.1 Environmental impact assessment of interventions on agricultural soils

Description of the agricultural systems

LH7. ATLANTIC AGRICULTURAL SOIL: REGENERATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT FOR IMPROVED NUTRIENT CYCLES AND SOIL HEALTH

The LH7 focuses on an agriculture soil located in Betuwe, Netherlands. This area is characterized by an Atlantic climate, with an annual average temperature of 10.6 °C and approximately 848 mm of precipitation. Historically, this area has faced challenges related to soil compaction as well as soil and water pollution.

This Lighthouse consists of a 130-hectare farm managed using biodynamic and regenerative practices, where sustainable methods are applied to improve soil health, such as broad crop rotations, green manure, reduced tillage, and the use of nitrogen-fixing crops. Two farming practices will be compared with the aim of evaluating and quantifying the impact these practices have on soil health enhancement, comparing a **biodynamic and regenerative system** with a **conventional system**.

Regarding management practices, the biodynamic and regenerative system relies on organic seeds, green manures and reduced tillage, with lower fuel consumption and no use of chemical inputs. In contrast, the conventional system uses conventional seeds, mineral fertilizers, herbicides and fungicides, with higher diesel consumption and reliance on external inputs for pest control and soil fertility.

Figure 4. LH7 overview: representative of high soil health.

LL1. MEDITERRANEAN AGRICULTURAL SOIL: ALTERNATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT AS POTENTIAL CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION

The LL1 focuses on agricultural management in the Mediterranean region of Sardinia, Italy, where climatic and environmental conditions are being altered by climate change. The area faces threats such as land abandonment due to low profitability of agricultural activities, soil fertility reduction, water scarcity, and extreme weather events. In this context, alternative management practices are being implemented to mitigate the effects of climate change and improve the sustainability of agriculture in the region.

Ussana and **Benatzu** are two experimental sites located in Sardinia that practice **conservation agriculture**, but with differences in soil fertility and management types. Both areas share practices such as reduced tillage, direct seeding or sod seeding, and crop rotation with legumes like faba beans and field peas, which promote soil health and contribute to sustainability.

A LCA will be conducted to compare the environmental impacts associated with different soil management practices — conventional tillage, reduced tillage, and sod seeding — implemented in the experimental sites of Ussana and Benatzu. The LCA results presented correspond to the agricultural practices implemented at both sites. Since exactly the same practices are applied in both zones (same inputs consumption, fuel consumption machinery working hours, etc.), the environmental impact of the three management practices analysed does not vary between soil types. The analysis quantifies only the impact of agricultural management operations and does not account for soil behaviour or productivity differences between sites. Therefore, the reported results are equally applicable to both Ussana and Benatzu.

Both sites adopt the same conservation agriculture practices, aiming to improve soil health and sustainability. However, there are differences in crop production between the two sites mainly due to their contrasting field and soil conditions: Ussana presents medium-low fertility soils (Luvisol) while Benatzu, characterized by medium-high fertility soils (Cambisol), offers a more favourable environment for crop growth and resilience against climate change impacts. Both areas have an average annual temperature of 17°C and 464 mm of precipitation.

Figure 5. LL1 overview: Benatzu and Ussana experimental sites.

LL2. CONTINENTAL AGRICULTURAL SOIL: CLIMATE MITIGATION THROUGH SOIL ORGANIC MATTER ACCUMULATION AND BUILT-UP

The LL2 focuses on agricultural soil located in Baselland, Switzerland, characterized by a continental climate, with an average precipitation of 890 mm and an annual average temperature of 10.6°C. The region faces several challenges, such as soil biodiversity loss, degradation of soil organic matter, erosion risks, and soil and water pollution due to intensive farming practices.

Through the LCA, the comparison of two experimental sites is made to assess the environmental impacts and the effectiveness of different agricultural management practices.

Experimental site 1 (biodynamic farming system): a highly innovative system that uses a wide variety of crops with minimal tillage, focused on sustainability and improving soil health. The different plots include:

- Faba bean and triticale cultivation: crop production with mulching, shallow tillage, and organic fertilization, followed by harvesting at the end of the cycle [LL2_1-3].
- Mountain lentils and naked oats cultivation: like the first plot, but with additional wing cultivation and mechanical weed control. Also, crops are harvested at the end of the cycle [LL2_4-6].
- Nectar production crops: primarily focused on biodiversity and pollination, this plot is not harvested and aims to support pollinators by producing nectar [LL2_7-9].
- No harvest – SOM accumulation: unlike the other plots, no crops are harvested here. The goal is to accumulate organic matter to enhance long-term soil health and fertility [LL2_13-15].

Experimental site 2 (intensive conventional farming system): a system that relies on conventional farming practices with a combination of reduced and conventional tillage. Fertilization is carried out with a mix of manure and mineral fertilizers. The crops include three plots:

- Arable plots with barley [LL2_16-18].
- Intensive fodder production on grassland and autumn grazing [LL2_19-21].
- Arable plots with wheat [LL2_22-24].

Figure 6. LL2 overview: experimental sites.

Life Cycle Inventory and assumptions

SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

The system boundaries are defined using the cradle-to-gate approach. The environmental assessment for the agricultural practices includes the extraction of raw materials such as fossil fuels, fertilizers (both organic and inorganic), seeds, water, and other materials necessary for cultivation. The assessment also includes manufacturing processes, usage (including diesel consumption, equipment operation, and emissions from machinery), maintenance (covering the upkeep of agricultural equipment and soil amendments), and the final disposal of machinery and materials at the end of their service life.

FUNCTIONAL UNIT

The functional unit adopted for this assessment is 1 hectare of managed soil under agricultural use. All data related to energy consumption, transportation, inputs and processes are normalized to this area, allowing for a direct comparison of environmental impacts across different agricultural practices and scenarios.

ALLOCATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL BURDENS

Since the LCA focuses exclusively on the agricultural practices applied at the case studies, all environmental burdens are directly attributed to these practices. This includes impacts from the production, transportation, and application of fertilizers, seeds, water, and other inputs, which are fully accounted for within the 1-hectare functional unit.

LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY

The following tables present the life cycle inventory of the agricultural practices carried out at the experimental sites under study. These inventories include detailed information on the inputs and key management practices applied to improve soil health. The data consists of primary sources, gathered through field assessments and surveys of land management practitioners, and secondary sources, derived from the Ecoinvent® database 3.10v, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the sustainable agricultural strategies implemented. The complete inventory can be consulted in the Annex of this deliverable.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The environmental impact evaluation was performed using the **ReCiPe 2016 Hierarchist Midpoint** method. The set of impact categories commonly used in the scientific literature for environmental analysis of agricultural systems was considered (Rebolledo-Leiva et al., 2022): global warming, stratospheric ozone depletion, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, marine eutrophication, terrestrial ecotoxicity, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine ecotoxicity, and fossil resource scarcity.

Abbreviations and units for the selected impact categories are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Impact categories used in the study offered by ReCiPe midpoint method.

Environmental impact category	Unit	Abbreviation
Global warming	kg CO ₂ -eq	GWP
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC ₁₁ -eq	SOD
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ -eq	TA
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P-eq	FE
Marine eutrophication	kg N-eq	ME
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	TET
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	FET
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	MET
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil-eq	FRS

Interpretation of results

LH7. ATLANTIC AGRICULTURAL SOIL: REGENERATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT FOR IMPROVED NUTRIENT CYCLES AND SOIL HEALTH

The environmental impacts of agricultural management practices in LH7, as evaluated using the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization, are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of agricultural practices in LH7. FU: 1 ha of managed agricultural soil.

Impact category	GW	SOD	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg CFC ₁₁ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
Total (conventional) ¹	767.45	0.0021	3.47	0.12	0.44	1,743.25	3.31	3.98	213.24
Total (biodynamic) ²	328.03	0.0015	2.83	0.03	0.86	384.26	0.66	1.05	86.38

¹Conventional system

²Biodynamic and regenerative system

Figure 7. Comparison of environmental impacts between conventional and organic (biodynamic and regenerative) cultivation systems in LH7.

The results of the environmental assessment of agricultural practices in LH7 show a significant reduction in environmental impacts when comparing the conventional system with the biodynamic and regenerative management. In particular, the global warming potential decreased from 767.45 kg CO₂-eq/ha in the conventional system to 328.03 kg CO₂-eq/ha in the biodynamic system, representing a 60% reduction.

These results reflect a lower dependence on external inputs and improved nutrient and soil management, highlighting the potential of regenerative agricultural practices to enhance soil health and reduce environmental impacts in urban settings.

The following graphs illustrate the relative contribution of each LH7 farming system—conventional (Figure 8) and biodynamic and regenerative (Figure 9) — to the different environmental impact categories, allowing for a comparative analysis of their environmental performance and identifying the most impactful processes within each management approach.

Figure 8. Contribution of conventional cultivation processes in LH7 to the different environmental impact categories.

Figure 9. Contribution of biodynamic and regenerative system cultivation in LH7 to the different environmental impact categories.

The results indicate that, in both LH7 farming systems analysed, diesel consumption and barley seed production are the dominant contributors across most environmental impact categories. Diesel use shows a particularly strong influence on GWP, TA, and FRS, reflecting the energy-intensive nature of field operations.

In the biodynamic and regenerative system, the application of organic manure shows a moderate contribution, mainly affecting nutrient-related impact categories, but less pronounced than the observed for mineral fertilisation in the conventional system.

Overall, the comparison indicates that the biodynamic and regenerative system reduces the relative contribution of high-impact external inputs—such as synthetic fertilisers and pesticides—resulting in a more evenly distributed impact profile. However, it also

highlights the increased relative importance of seed production and machinery use, underlining the need for targeted improvements in these processes to further enhance environmental performance.

LL1. MEDITERRANEAN AGRICULTURAL SOIL: ALTERNATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT AS POTENTIAL CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION

The environmental impacts of agricultural management practices in LL1, as evaluated using the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization, are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of agricultural practices in LL1. FU: 1 ha of managed agricultural soil.

Impact category	GW	SOD	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg CFC ₁₁ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
Conventional tillage	698.12	0.0026	3.41	0.14	0.42	3,251.24	3.18	6.29	224.57
Reduced tillage	555.14	0.0026	2.81	0.14	0.42	3,078.99	3.10	6.06	176.86
Sod seeding	539.66	0.0026	2.74	0.14	0.42	3,060.79	3.09	6.04	172.48

Figure 10. Environmental impact comparison of soil management practices in LL1: conventional tillage, reduced tillage, and sod seeding.

The analysis of environmental impacts associated with soil management practices in LL1 shows that sod seeding has the lowest impact in all categories, with lower CO₂ emissions compared to both reduced tillage and conventional tillage. While conventional tillage shows the highest impacts in terms of CO₂ emissions and fossil resource scarcity, reduced tillage offers a moderate improvement.

The following figures provide a detailed analysis of the environmental impacts of the three soil management practices, highlighting the activities that contribute most to each impact category. The key difference between the three systems — conventional tillage, reduced tillage and sod seeding — lies in the soil preparation phase, which determines their respective environmental performance.

In the **conventional tillage system** (Figure 11), soil preparation generates a significant environmental impact due to intensive operations such as ploughing and harrowing for seedbed preparation. In contrast, the **reduced tillage system** (Figure 12) shows a lower impact in this stage, as only harrowing is performed, reducing soil disturbance and energy requirements. Finally, the **sod seeding system** (Figure 13) avoids soil preparation activities altogether, leading to a substantial reduction in environmental impacts, particularly in the GWP category, because of minimizing fuel consumption and soil disturbance.

Figure 11. Contribution of conventional tillage system to environmental impact categories.

Figure 12. Contribution of reduced tillage system to environmental impact categories.

Figure 13. Contribution of sod seeding system to environmental impact categories.

LL2. CONTINENTAL AGRICULTURAL SOIL: CLIMATE MITIGATION THROUGH SOIL ORGANIC MATTER ACCUMULATION AND BUILT-UP

The environmental impacts of agricultural management practices at the two experimental sites in LL2, which include biodynamic and intensive conventional farming systems, are assessed using the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization method. The results are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6, respectively.

Table 5. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of biodynamic farming systems in LL2. FU: 1 ha of managed agricultural soil.

Impact category	GW	SOD	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg CFC ₁₁ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
LL2_1-3 ¹	777.41	5.16·10 ⁻⁴	5.14	0.10	0.16	4,718.81	34.83	48.90	370.50
LL2_4-6 ²	648.43	7.75·10 ⁻⁴	4.47	0.10	0.20	3,781.67	33.05	45.69	276.18
LL2_7-9 ³	1,523.38	3.93·10 ⁻⁴	4.32	0.03	0.04	1,740.76	1.50	3.77	1,215.79
LL2_13-15 ⁴	311.81	2.19·10 ⁻³	1.94	0.03	0.44	1,055.51	1.63	2.63	72.67

¹[LL2_1-3]: Faba bean and triticale cultivation

²[LL2_4-6]: Mountain lentils and naked oats cultivation

³[LL2_7-9]: Nectar production crops

⁴[LL2_13-15]: No harvest – SOM accumulation

Table 6. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of intensive conventional farming systems in LL2. FU: 1 ha of managed agricultural soil.

Impact category	GW	SOD	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg CFC ₁₁ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
LL2_16-18 ¹	304.36	1.38·10 ⁻³	1.39	0.04	0.47	628.40	1.24	1.91	148.48
LL2_19-21 ²	90.35	3.27·10 ⁻⁵	0.39	5.36·10 ⁻⁴	7.55·10 ⁻⁴	95.79	0.04	0.12	25.67
LL2_22-24 ³	1,691.23	1.71·10 ⁻³	5.65	0.19	0.52	2,501.27	3.83	7.33	1,261.31

¹[LL2_16-18]: Arable plots with barley

²[LL2_19-21]: Intensive fodder production on grassland and autumn grazing

³[LL2_22-24]: Arable plots with wheat

Based on the LCA results, **biodynamic and conventional farming systems** (Figure 14) show notable variability in environmental impacts depending on plot and crop type. Some plots demonstrate low greenhouse gas emissions and fossil resource use, highlighting the benefits of organic matter accumulation and reduced mechanization. However, certain plots exhibit higher nitrogen eutrophication and terrestrial ecotoxicity, likely linked to fertilization practices. Overall, careful management of fertilizers and crop selection is key to maximizing environmental benefits and minimizing hotspots in biodynamic systems.

Figure 14. Environmental impact (GWP) of soil management practices in LL2.

The environmental impacts in both **LL2_1-3 (faba bean and triticale)** (Figure 15) and **LL2_4-6 (mountain lentils and naked oats)** (Figure 16) are primarily driven by fertilization, particularly in toxicity indicators (TET, FET, MET) where it exceeds 90%. In LL2_1-3, this is associated with the use of processed organic fertilizers, while in LL2_4-6, mineral fertilizers for soil conditioning represent the main impact source. Soil preparation contributes significantly to GWP and FRS (20-30%) in both systems due to diesel consumption from tillage operations, while sowing and harvesting represent minor contributions across all impact categories.

Figure 15. Contribution of faba bean and triticale cultivation [LL2_1-3] to the different environmental impact categories.

Figure 16. Contribution of mountain lentils and naked oats cultivation [LL2_4-6] to the different environmental impact categories.

The environmental impacts in **LL2_7-9 (nectar production crops)** (Figure 17) are associated exclusively with tillage and sowing operations, as no fertilization, pesticides, or harvesting are applied in this system. The diesel consumption from these operations represents the primary source of environmental impact. The simplicity of this management approach—establishing a flowering cover crop for pollinators without subsequent interventions—results in a low-impact profile driven entirely by the initial soil preparation and seeding phases.

Figure 17. Contribution of nectar production crops [LL2_7-9] to the different environmental impact categories.

LL2_13-15 (Figure 18) is a **soil organic matter accumulation** system with no harvest, where biomass remains in the field. Impacts are dominated by sowing operations (65% of GWP, nearly 100% of other categories) due to the diverse seed mixture application, while

fertilization contributes significantly only to TET (80%). The absence of harvesting results in a low-impact profile focused on soil restoration

Figure 18. Contribution of SOM accumulation [LL2_13-15] to the different environmental impact categories.

The three conventional systems show significantly different environmental profiles despite all being classified as intensive farming. **LL2_19-21 (grassland fodder production)** (Figure 20) presents the lowest impacts due to the absence of soil tillage, mineral fertilization, and pesticides, with only slurry application and grass mowing required.

LL2_16-18 (barley) (Figure 19) represents a minimal-intervention annual cropping system where sowing and fertilization operations dominate most impact categories, while soil preparation contributes significantly to GWP (42%) and FRS (70%) due to diesel consumption from tillage operations.

In contrast, **LL2_22-24 (wheat)** (Figure 21) exemplifies intensive annual cropping, with an impact 5 times higher than barley in the GWP category. The wheat system shows impacts distributed across multiple operations: soil preparation dominates GWP (55%) and FRS (60%) due to intensive tillage operations (mulching and deep ploughing), while fertilization and weed control are the main contributors to toxicity categories.

This pattern reflects a multi-operation intensive management system with high fuel consumption and extensive inputs, contrasting with the simpler operational profiles of barley and grassland systems.

Figure 19. Contribution of arable plots with barley [LL2_16-18] to the different environmental impact categories.

Figure 20. Contribution of intensive fodder production on grassland and autumn grazing [LL2_19-21] to the different environmental impact categories.

Figure 21. Contribution of arable plots with wheat [LL2_22-24] to the different environmental impact categories.

2.2 Environmental impact assessment of interventions on forestry soils

Description of the forestry systems under study

LH1. MEDITERRANEAN FORESTRY SOIL - DEHESA EL BALDÍO DE TALAVÁN: RESTORATION OF SOIL BY ROTATIONAL GRAZING MANAGING IN WOODY PASTURES

The LH1 is a forestry soil located in Extremadura, Spain. This area is characterized by a Mediterranean climate, with an annual average temperature of 16.7 °C and approximately 644 mm of precipitation. The area faces soil threats such as low biodiversity, erosion, overgrazing, low soil quality, reduced soil organic matter, and landscape simplification.

A **site with high soil health** (232 ha) is managed through sustainable practices, including rotational grazing, absence of sowing and tillage, short periods of high-intensity grazing followed by adequate resting time, and the use of autochthonous breeds such as the Blanca Cacereña cattle and Merina Negra sheep. The main vegetation includes leguminous plants, grasses, holm oaks and a well-developed shrub layer. The main economic activity is cow meat production.

In contrast, a **nearby control area with low soil health** (18.1 ha) presents the same vegetation structure (dehesa ecosystem) but has been subject to reforestation, continuous tillage over the years, and absence of livestock, resulting in lower soil quality.

A comparison between both areas was performed through LCA to assess the environmental impacts associated with their contrasting management practices and soil health conditions.

Figure 22. LH1 overview: comparison of high (left) and low (right) soil health areas.

LH6. BOREAL FORESTRY SOIL: EFFECT OF FERTILIZATION, SELECTION OF SPECIES, TREE BREEDING AND SUSTAINABLE SOIL MANAGEMENT

The LH6 focuses on a boreal forestry soil located in Latvia. This area is characterized by a boreal climate, with an annual average temperature of 5.9 °C and approximately 700 mm of precipitation. The main soil threats in this area include low below- and aboveground biodiversity, erosion, GHG emissions, low soil quality with risk of nutrient deficiency, low soil organic matter content, landscape simplification, soil acidity, and inappropriate groundwater levels.

Since 2001, the area representative of **high soil health** has been designated as a research territory, where **sustainable management practices have been implemented to maintain high soil health**. These practices include nutrient balance management, reforestation to promote vegetation cover, tending to improve light conditions for specific species, and gentle soil preparation techniques.

In contrast, the **control area is a former sand and gravel mining site with poor soil health**, affected by erosion, nutrient depletion, and ultra-humid conditions. Unlike the reforested area, no active restoration measures are applied. Currently, there is no economic activity in the mining site, although monitoring activities are being conducted to evaluate soil health dynamics.

Figure 23. LH6 overview: comparison of high (left) and low (right) soil health areas.

Life Cycle Inventory and assumptions

SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

The system boundaries are defined using the cradle-to-gate approach. The environmental assessment for the soil restoration processes includes the extraction of raw materials (such as fossil fuels and minerals), manufacturing processes of raw material, usage (diesel consumption, equipment operation, and emissions from machinery use), maintenance, and the final disposal of machinery and materials at the end of their service life.

FUNCTIONAL UNIT

The functional unit adopted is 1 hectare of soil under management. All data regarding energy consumption, transportation, inputs, and processes are normalized to this area, facilitating direct comparison of environmental impacts among different scenarios.

ALLOCATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL BURDENS

Since this LCA focuses exclusively on the restoration process, all environmental burdens are directly attributed to restoration activities. This includes impacts from production, transportation, and input application, as well as the restoration efforts themselves. All these impacts are accounted for within the 1 ha functional unit.

LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY

The following tables present the life cycle inventory of the soil restoration processes carried out in the LH1 and LH6 case studies. These inventories include detailed information on the inputs and key management practices applied to improve soil health. The data consists of primary sources, gathered through field assessments and surveys of land management practitioners, and secondary sources, derived from the Ecoinvent® database 3.10v, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the remediation strategies implemented. The complete inventory can be consulted in the Annex of this deliverable.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The environmental impact evaluation was performed using the **ReCiPe 2016 Hierarchist Midpoint** method. The impact categories were selected from those recommended by the ILCD Handbook (European Commission, 2010), taking into account the most commonly used for LCA applied to soil restoration.

The following environmental impact potentials were assessed: acidification potential, eutrophication potential, and global warming potential. Additionally, an energy analysis was conducted, focusing on the cumulative demand for non-renewable fossil energy. These impact categories were selected as they are among the most commonly reported in LCA studies of forest systems (González-García et al., 2014). Abbreviations and units for the nine selected impact categories are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Impact categories used in the study offered by ReCiPe midpoint method.

Environmental impact category	Unit	Abbreviation
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	GWP
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	TA
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	FE
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	ME
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	TET
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	FET
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	MET
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	HNCT
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	FRS

Interpretation of results

LH1. DEHESA EL BALDÍO DE TALAVÁN

The results from the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization for the environmental impacts of the soil management practices in LH1 are summarized in Table 8.

Table 8. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of forestry soil restoration in LH1. FU: 1 ha of managed soil.

Impact category	GW	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	HNCT	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
Total	928.88	5.10	0.06	1.40	490.51	1.42	2.14	1,647.66	44.22

The system includes livestock to account for impacts directly related to rotational grazing management. Livestock-related inputs include water consumption, feed supply, and direct emissions (enteric methane and nitrogen emissions from manure), calculated

according to IPCC guidelines. This modelling approach ensures that only impacts attributable to soil management practices are considered, avoiding double counting. Machinery used for pasture management is also included.

With a **GWP of 928.88 kg CO₂ eq**, greenhouse gas emissions represent a significant impact, although rotational grazing management could mitigate this effect in the long term by enhancing soil carbon sequestration. The HNCT, with 1,647.66 kg 1,4-DCB eq, and TET, with 490.51 kg 1,4-DCB eq, indicates a potential risk to soil organisms. This could be associated with heavy metals, residual veterinary compounds or nutrient imbalances in the soil due to previous agricultural practices that negatively affect soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions.

Additionally, although to a lesser extent, marine eutrophication (ME) highlights the potential nitrogen pollution, which could affect water quality in the surrounding ecosystem.

Figure 24 shows the contribution analysis of the different steps involved in the soil management process at LH1.

Figure 24. Contribution of LH1 soil management to environmental impact categories.

The highest environmental impact comes from livestock management since cattle generate a significant impact due to their methane emissions, high feed and water consumption, and manure production.

Additionally, feed supply for livestock also plays an important role across all categories, highlighting the importance of the origin and type of forage used. To a lesser extent, the diesel consumption for the machinery use contribute to terrestrial toxicity and resource depletion.

LH6. BOREAL FORESTRY SOIL

The results from the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization for the environmental impacts of the soil management practices in LH6 are summarized in Table 9.

Table 9. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of industrial soil restoration in LH6. FU: 1 ha of remediated soil.

Impact category	GW	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	HNCT	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
Total	312.09	1.05	0.03	0.005	1,201.95	3,24	5.11	194.95	95.52

The LCA results for LH6 show relatively low environmental impacts, with a GWP of 312.09 kg CO₂-eq per hectare of remediated soil, primarily associated with machinery use during recultivation and planting operations. The system does not involve fertilization or livestock, resulting in minimal greenhouse gas emissions. The most notable impact is terrestrial ecotoxicity (TET: 1,201.95 kg 1,4-DCB eq), likely related to soil conditioning materials and plant protection products used during restoration. Fossil resource scarcity (FRS: 95.52 kg oil-eq) reflects diesel consumption from machinery operations. Overall, this forestry restoration system presents a low environmental profile, with the main concern being terrestrial toxicity from chemical inputs in the revegetation process.

Figure 25 shows the contribution analysis of the different steps involved in soil management process at LH6.

Figure 25. Contribution of LH6 soil restoration process to environmental impact categories.

Regarding Figure 25, an impact of recultivation process is observed mainly due to the use of machinery, especially the digger. In addition, the planting process has also an important impact due to the tree seedling production in heated greenhouses. The soil conditioning has a weighty role too due to the high environmental impact of the soil pH raising agent (CaCO_3) that is primarily associated with lime extraction and processing. This process involves high energy consumption and CO_2 emissions from calcination. Additionally, transport task plays a significant role.

2.3 Environmental impact assessment of interventions on urban soils

Description of the urban systems under study

LH4. CONTINENTAL URBAN SOIL: CARBON SEQUESTRATION AND FLOOD MITIGATION CAPACITY OF AGRICULTURAL AND FOREST USES IN URBAN SOILS

The LH4 site is located in Zagreb, Croatia, an area characterized by a temperate continental climate with an annual average temperature ranging from 6.2°C to 11.4°C and approximately 859 mm of precipitation. Historically, the soil in this region suffered from overexploitation, low biodiversity, structural degradation, soil compaction, abandonment, increased flood risk, and low organic matter content. The primary challenge in this area is the restoration of soil health through sustainable management practices. These practices, such as mulching, minimal soil disturbance, permanent grass cover, and appropriate fertilization, have significantly improved soil health.

To address these challenges, the forestry has been divided into four distinct areas, each employing different sustainable management practices aimed at improving soil health, along with a nearby control area for comparison.

The first area is a **1-hectare apple orchard**, where sustainable management practices are implemented to maintain high soil health. These practices include mulching, minimal soil disturbance, permanent grass cover, and appropriate fertilization. The main economic activity in this area is apple production.

The second area, also **1 hectare**, is a **grassland** consisting of a grass-clover mixture. Sustainable practices here include mulching, no soil disturbance, and permanent vegetation cover. This area does not have any direct economic value but contributes significantly to soil health.

The third area is a **50-hectare forest** dedicated to wood production. In this forest, sustainable practices focus on maintaining soil health by avoiding soil disturbance, refraining from mineral fertilization, and allowing the natural decay of trees and leaves. The main economic activity in this area is the production of wood.

The fourth area is **1 hectare of abandoned agricultural land** that has transitioned to a secondary forest with shrubbery. No soil disturbance occurs in this area, which helps support the natural regeneration of vegetation and the improvement of soil quality. There is no economic activity in this area.

Finally, there is a **nearby 20-hectare control area with low soil health**, primarily used for intensive annual cropping. The crops grown include winter wheat, winter barley, winter oats, soybean, and maize. The management practices here, such as conventional tillage, intensive mineral fertilization, and the lack of organic fertilization or cover cropping, have contributed to a decline in soil health.

A LCA is carried out to compare the environmental impacts of several management practices applied in the areas described above.

Figure 26. LH4 overview.

LH5. BOREAL URBAN SOIL: IMPACT OF URBAN AGRICULTURE ON SOIL HEALTH

The LH5 site is located in Vilnius, Lithuania, where urban agriculture is practiced on soils experiencing a boreal climate. The average annual temperature is 7.2°C, with approximately 764 mm of precipitation. The primary soil threats in this area include flood risk, soil erosion, compaction, pollution, reduced biodiversity, and low organic matter content.

The main challenge in this area is restoring soil health through the implementation of **sustainable urban gardening practices**. The garden features a variety of crops, such as cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkin, and strawberries. To improve soil health, sustainable practices including composting, mulching, no-tillage, and the avoidance of agrochemicals have been adopted.

In contrast, a **0.96-hectare control area** has been established, **covered with a lawn and intensively managed grass**, but without any economic activity. This area serves as a comparison site to evaluate the impact of urban gardening on soil restoration and sustainability.

Figure 27. LH5 overview: urban garden representing high soil health (top) and nearby control area with low soil health (lawn) (bottom).

Life Cycle Inventory and assumptions

SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

The system boundaries are defined using the cradle-to-gate approach. The environmental assessment for agricultural practices in urban soils includes the extraction of raw materials such as fossil fuels, minerals, fertilizers (both organic and inorganic), seeds, water, and other materials necessary for cultivation. The assessment also encompasses manufacturing processes, usage (including diesel consumption, equipment operation, and emissions from machinery), maintenance (covering the upkeep of agricultural equipment and soil amendments), and the final disposal of machinery and materials at the end of their service life.

FUNCTIONAL UNIT

The functional unit adopted for this assessment is 1 hectare of urban soil under agricultural use. All data related to energy consumption, transportation, inputs and

processes are normalized to this area, allowing for a direct comparison of environmental impacts across different agricultural practices and scenarios.

ALLOCATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL BURDENS

Since the LCA focuses exclusively on agricultural practices applied to urban soils, all environmental burdens are directly attributed to these practices. This includes impacts from the production, transportation, and application of fertilizers, seeds, water, and other inputs, which are fully accounted for within the 1-hectare functional unit.

LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY

The following tables present the life cycle inventory of the agricultural practices carried out in urban soils. These inventories include detailed information on the inputs and key management practices applied to improve soil health. The data consists of primary sources, gathered through field assessments and surveys of land management practitioners, and secondary sources, derived from the Ecoinvent® database 3.10v, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the sustainable agricultural strategies implemented. The complete inventory can be consulted in the Annex of this deliverable.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The environmental impact evaluation was performed using the **ReCiPe 2016 Hierarchist Midpoint** method. The impact categories were selected taking into account the most commonly used for LCA applied to agricultural soils, as outlined by Cámara-Salim et al. (2021).

The selection of environmental impact categories for this type of study includes Climate Change, Particulate Matter, Terrestrial Acidification, Freshwater Eutrophication, Marine Eutrophication, Human Toxicity, Land Use, and Fossil Depletion.

Abbreviations and units for the nine selected impact categories are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Impact categories used in the study offered by ReCiPe midpoint method.

Environmental impact category	Unit	Abbreviation
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	GWP
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM _{2.5} eq	PM
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	TA
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	FE
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	ME
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	TET
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	HCT
Land use	m ² a crop eq	LU
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	FRS

Interpretation of results

LH4. CONTINENTAL URBAN SOIL

The results from the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization for the environmental impacts of the soil management practices in LH4 are summarized in Table 11.

Table 11. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis agricultural practices in LH4. FU: 1 ha.

Impact category	GW	PM	TA	FE	ME	TET	HCT	LU	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg PM _{2.5} -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	m ² a crop eq	kg oil-eq
Total (Apple orchard)	1,482.11	2.10	5.90	0.15	0.12	4,400.97	16.64	16.70	671.79
Total (grassland)	99.20	0.23	0.51	0.003	0.003	197.15	0.35	0.15	99.89
Total (Annual cropland)	1,284.64	1.98	6.08	0.20	0.55	4,807.40	8.85	725.09	451.21

Sustainable urban soil management, particularly in grasslands and forests, drastically reduces environmental impacts compared to intensive cropland or managed orchards. While the apple orchard shows higher impacts due to input-intensive management, the forested and grassland areas demonstrate that minimal disturbance, permanent vegetation cover, and careful input management can maintain soil health while minimizing environmental burdens.

In the apple orchard (Figure 28), the **fertilizer application stage** is the dominant contributor to most environmental impact categories, including greenhouse gas emissions, terrestrial acidification, and human toxicity. This indicates that, despite sustainable management practices such as mulching and minimal soil disturbance, input-intensive operations drive the majority of environmental burdens.

For **intensive annual cropping** (Figure 29), the **land preparation and sowing operations** show the highest impacts across all categories. A closer inspection of the land preparation stage (Figure 30) reveals that **fertilizer application within this stage** is responsible for the largest share of impacts, confirming that mineral fertilizer use is the main environmental hotspot in both managed and conventional cropping systems.

Figure 28. Contribution of apple orchard at LH4 urban soil to environmental impact categories.

Figure 29. Contribution of intensive annual cropping at LH4 urban soil to environmental impact categories.

Figure 30. Contribution of land preparation stage in intensive annual cropping at LH4 to environmental impact categories.

These findings highlight that, in LH4 urban soils, minimizing fertilizer inputs or optimizing their use is critical to reducing environmental impacts, even in systems otherwise managed sustainably.

LH5. BOREAL URBAN SOIL

The results from the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization for the environmental impacts of the soil management practices in LH5 are summarized in Table 12.

Table 12. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of the agricultural soil in LH5. FU: 1 ha

Impact category	GW	PM	TA	FE	ME	TET	HCT	LU	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg PM _{2.5} -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	m ² a crop eq	kg oil-eq
Total	14.05	0.0214	0.0417	0.0008	0.0002	27.27	0.14	0.54	4.50

The most relevant impact categories include Global Warming Potential (14.05 kg CO₂ eq), reflecting moderate emissions mainly from soil processes and machinery, and Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (27.27 kg 1,4-DCB), likely influenced by historical contamination. Minimal eutrophication (FE & ME) and low acidification (0.0417 kg SO₂ eq) indicate efficient nutrient cycling with reduced runoff. Additionally, low fossil resource use (4.50 kg oil eq) highlights energy-efficient management.

Figure 31 shows the contribution analysis of the different steps involved in the soil remediation process at LH5. In the graph, the influence of land management is clearly

observed, mainly driven by the use of machinery, particularly the motor mower. Fertilisation also represents a significant contribution, due to the application of compost as the primary fertiliser. Finally, the seeding stage emerges as an important contributor, especially in certain impact categories, which can be attributed to seed production in heated greenhouses.

Figure 31. Contribution of LH5 urban agricultural soil to environmental impact categories.

2.4 Environmental impact assessment of interventions on industrial soils

Description of the systems under study

LH2. MEDITERRANEAN INDUSTRIAL SOIL - SANTA ANTONIETA MINE: RESTORATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL BY MINING ACTIVITIES USING ARTIFICIAL SOILS (TECHNOSOLS)

The LH2 focuses on a former industrial site located in Cartagena, Spain, within the historic Cartagena-La Unión mining district. This area is characterized by a Mediterranean climate, with an annual average temperature of 17.5 °C and approximately 280 mm of precipitation. Historically, intensive mining activities in this district have led to severe soil degradation, including heavy metal contamination (specifically Cd, Cu, Pb, Zn, and As), as well as issues of acidification, sulfation, and salinization, which have collectively resulted in the near-total loss of vegetation cover.

To address these challenges, the **remediation strategy implemented in 2012 involved the application of technosols**—artificial soils formulated using a blend of mining tailings, marble waste, and manure. This industrial soil was combined with an assisted phytostabilization approach, in which heavy metal-tolerant plant species are used alongside organic and inorganic amendments to chemically stabilize contaminants and reduce their bioavailability. As a result, a 1-hectare area was remediated, establishing a resilient Mediterranean shrubland featuring species such as *Piptaterum miliaceum*, *Salvia rosmarinus*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, *Dittrichia viscosa*, and *Hyparrhenia hirta*. In contrast, a **nearby**

5-hectare control area remains unremediated, exhibiting the persistent adverse effects of past mining activities, including the absence of vegetation and overall poor soil quality.

Figure 32. LH2 overview: representative of high soil health (left) and low soil health (control area) (right).

LH3. ATLANTIC INDUSTRIAL SOIL - TOURO MINE: RESTORATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL BY COPPER MINING ACTIVITIES USING ARTIFICIAL SOILS (TECHNOSOLS)

The case study of the Touro mine in Galicia, Spain, focuses on the restoration of contaminated soil resulting from copper mining activities. The site is located in an industrial area that has been heavily impacted by past mining operations, leading to severe soil degradation. The region is characterized by an Atlantic climate, with an average annual temperature of 12.7 °C and a high annual rainfall of 1242 mm. The soil is classified as technosols, which are managed to mitigate the hazardous properties of contamination.

The area faces multiple challenges including soil and water pollution, hyperacidification, hyperoxidation (with high Fe^{3+} content), hypersulfation, hyperaluminization, and metallic contamination (notably Mn, Cu, Zn, and Ni). Additionally, the site exhibits characteristics of extremophile ecosystems and bio-catalysis acceleration due to oxygen-reduction reactions, which further complicate soil recovery.

The remediation strategy involves the production of artificial soils (Technosols) specifically designed to mitigate the adverse effects of copper mining contamination. These artificial soils are formulated to improve soil structure and fertility, neutralize acidity and immobilize heavy metals.

The intervention spans 30 hectares, with restoration efforts assessed through an LCA, compared to a nearby 15-hectare control area that continues to exhibit poor soil health.

Figure 33. LH3 overview: representative of high soil health (left) and low soil health (control area) (right).

Life Cycle Inventory and assumptions

SYSTEM BOUNDARIES

The system boundaries are defined using the cradle-to-gate approach. The environmental assessment for the soil remediation process includes the extraction of raw materials (such as fossil fuels and minerals), manufacturing processes (remediation-related materials), usage (diesel consumption, equipment operation, and emissions from machinery use), maintenance (upkeep of remediation equipment and soil amendments), and the final disposal of machinery and materials at the end of their service life.

FUNCTIONAL UNIT

The functional unit adopted is 1 hectare of remediated soil. All data regarding energy consumption, transportation, inputs, and processes are normalized to this area, facilitating direct comparison of environmental impacts among different scenarios.

ALLOCATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL BURDENS

Since the LCA focuses exclusively on the remediation process without the generation of co-products, all environmental burdens are directly assigned to the remediation process. This means that impacts from the production, transportation, and application of inputs, as well as the activities related to assisted phytostabilization (LH2), are fully accounted for within the functional unit of 1 ha, without the need to distribute burdens among multiple products or functions.

LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY

The following tables present the life cycle inventory of the soil remediation processes carried out in the LH2 and LH3 case studies. These inventories include detailed information on the inputs and key management practices applied to improve soil health. The data consists of primary sources, gathered through field assessments and surveys of land management practitioners, and secondary sources, derived from the Ecoinvent® database 3.10v, ensuring a comprehensive assessment of the remediation strategies implemented. The complete inventory can be consulted in the Annex of this deliverable.

Direct emissions resulting from the application of Technosol to the soil—primarily biogeochemical emissions of N_2O and CH_4 linked to the mineralisation of organic matter—are not included in the life cycle inventory.

This decision is based on the high level of uncertainty associated with these emissions, which are strongly influenced by site-specific factors such as soil properties, water regime, aeration, temperature, microbial activity, and the temporal evolution of the system. In remediated mining soils, these variables exhibit particularly high spatial and temporal variability, and no standardised, site-specific emission factors are currently available to support a robust and representative quantification.

Furthermore, Tier 1 emission factors proposed by the IPCC are primarily designed for conventional agricultural soils. Their direct application to Technosol-based remediation systems is therefore limited and may result in significant over- or underestimation of actual emissions.

For these reasons, and in order to ensure methodological consistency, transparency, and robustness of the results, this study adopts a conservative approach by limiting the quantitative assessment to emissions associated with well-defined and measurable processes, such as material transport and machinery use during Technosol production and application.

Nevertheless, it is acknowledged that Technosol application may induce short- and medium-term biogeochemical emissions, as well as long-term environmental benefits related to soil quality improvement and reduced metal bioavailability. These aspects are addressed qualitatively in the discussion section of the study.

Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The environmental impact evaluation was performed using the **ReCiPe 2016 Hierarchist Midpoint** method. The impact categories were selected taking into account the most commonly used for LCA applied to soil remediation, as outlined by Visentin et al. (2019).

The selected impact categories include greenhouse gas emissions, quantified through the 100-year Global Warming Potential (GWP) category, acidification potential and eutrophication potential, which reflect the negative effects on air quality as well as both aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, and toxicity-related impacts, such as ecotoxicity potential and human toxicity potential, which address the effects of pollutants on ecosystems and human health. Additionally, Fossil Resource Scarcity (FRS) will also be analysed to assess the impact of the consumption of non-renewable energy resources, such as fossil fuels (oil, coal, and natural gas).

Abbreviations and units for the nine selected impact categories are shown in Table 13.

Table 13. Impact categories used in the study offered by ReCiPe midpoint method.

Environmental category	impact	Unit	Abbreviation
Global warming		kg CO ₂ eq	GWP
Terrestrial acidification		kg SO ₂ eq	TA
Freshwater eutrophication		kg P eq	FE
Marine eutrophication		kg N eq	ME
Terrestrial ecotoxicity		kg 1,4-DCB	TET
Freshwater ecotoxicity		kg 1,4-DCB	FET
Marine ecotoxicity		kg 1,4-DCB	MET
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity		kg 1,4-DCB	HNCT
Fossil resource scarcity		kg oil eq	FRS

Interpretation of results

LH2. SANTA ANTONIETA MINE

The results from the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization for the environmental impacts of the industrial soil remediation practices in LH2 (Santa Antonieta Mine) are summarized in Table 14.

Table 14. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of industrial soil remediation in LH2. FU: 1 ha of remediated soil.

Impact category	GW	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	HNCT	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
Total	326.27	1.39	0.066	0.007	893.87	2.13	3.83	412.33	92.96

The environmental impact analysis of LH2 for the remediation of 1 ha of mining soil indicates a Global Warming Potential (GWP) of 326.27 kg CO₂ eq, reflecting a carbon footprint primarily driven by fuel consumption and emissions associated with remediation activities, thereby contributing to climate change.

Terrestrial Ecotoxicity (TET) emerges as the most significant impact category, reaching 893.87 kg 1,4-DCB eq, which indicates substantial toxicity risks to terrestrial ecosystems. This impact is likely linked to residual soil contamination and the materials and inputs used during the remediation process.

Human Non-Carcinogenic Toxicity (HNCT) is also notable, with a value of 412.33 kg 1,4-DCB eq, raising concerns regarding potential human health risks resulting from exposure to toxic substances.

Fossil Resource Scarcity (FRS) amounts to 88.82 kg oil eq, highlighting a continued reliance on fossil fuel resources, particularly for machinery operation and material transport, which contributes to resource depletion.

Figure 34 shows the contribution analysis of the different steps involved in the soil remediation process at LH2.

Figure 34. Contribution of LH2 soil remediation process to environmental impact categories.

FE, ME, TET, FET, and MET are primarily influenced by the crop establishment phase, which accounts for more than 70% of the total impact. FRS is largely driven by the technosol application phase, contributing 37.67%, reflecting the reliance on fossil fuels for machinery and transportation. Likewise, TA and HNCT are significantly affected by technosol application, contributing 40.78% and 56.40% of the total impact, respectively.

The analysis of the crop establishment step (Figure 35) shows that the tree seedling phase accounts for nearly the entire impact within this process. This is mainly due to the environmental burden associated with tree seedling production in both heated and unheated greenhouses.

Figure 35. Contribution of the crop establishment process to the environmental impact categories in LH2.

LH3. TOURO MINE

The results from the ReCiPe Midpoint characterization for the environmental impacts of the industrial soil remediation practices in LH3 (Touro Mine) are summarized in Table 15.

Table 15. ReCiPe Midpoint characterization factors for environmental impact analysis of industrial soil remediation in LH3 FU: 1 ha of remediated soil.

Impact category	GW	TA	FE	ME	TET	FET	MET	HNCT	FRS
Units	kg CO ₂ -eq	kg SO ₂ -eq	kg P-eq	kg N-eq	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg 1,4-DCB	kg oil-eq
Total	8,812.04	34.17	0.071	0.056	42,893.51	11.30	37.03	29,700.30	2,624.41

The environmental analysis of the remediation process applied to the Touro mine follows a similar pattern to that of the Santa Antonieta mine in LH3. The most significant contributions are observed in TET, which reaches 42,893.51 kg 1,4-DCB eq, indicating substantial toxicity risks for terrestrial ecosystems, likely due to soil contamination and remediation inputs. HNCT is also notably high at 29,700.30 kg 1,4-DCB eq, raising concerns about potential health risks from exposure to pollutants. Additionally, GWP stands at 8,812.04 kg CO₂ eq, reflecting a high carbon footprint, likely driven by fuel consumption and emissions from machinery. The Fossil Resource Scarcity (FRS) impact is also significant at 2,624.41 kg oil eq, pointing to a strong dependence on fossil fuels for remediation activities.

Figure 36 illustrates the relative contribution of different remediation processes—technosol production and application—to various environmental impact categories in LH3 soil remediation.

Figure 36. Contribution of LH3 soil remediation processes to environmental impact categories.

Figure 37 focuses on the technosol application phase. An analysis of the technosol loading onto the truck, prior to its transport and field spreading, indicates that transport is the stage responsible for the majority of the environmental impact, clearly exceeding the contributions from both the loading and spreading operations.

Figure 37. Contribution of the technosol application phase to the environmental impact categories in LH3.

2.5 Uncertainty assessment of LCA results

This section describes the main sources of uncertainty associated with each impact category used in this study, identifies the LHs and LLs most affected, and summarises the practical implications for the interpretation of the LCA. The qualitative uncertainty level is assessed on a four-point scale: *low*, *moderate* and *high*.

Table 16. Uncertainty characterisation by impact category across InBestSoil case studies.

Impact category	Main uncertainty source	Most affected LH/LL	Consequence for LCA results	Level
GWP (kg CO₂-eq)	Exclusion of direct field emissions (N ₂ O, CH ₄) and SOC stock changes; use of generic IPCC emission factors, where direct emissions are included but estimated with average factors.	LH7 (biodynamic), LH1 (grazing), LL2 (SOM accumulation)	GWP underestimates the full climate benefit of regenerative systems and the full climate impact of livestock-based systems	HIGH
TET / HNCT (kg 1,4-DCB)	ReCiPe characterisation factors carry ±1–2 orders of magnitude uncertainty.	LH2, LH3 (mining soils), LH1 (livestock manure and feed supply compounds)	Absolute values are indicative only; suitable for relative comparison within the same case study, not across land use types	HIGH
FRS (kg oil-eq)	Transport distance estimates; Ecoinvent machinery lifespan allocation.	LH3 (technosol transport over 5 km)	Well-characterised process; moderate sensitivity to transport distance assumptions	MODERATE
FE / ME (kg P/N-eq)	N and P release rates from organic amendments depend on soil temperature, moisture and microbial activity.	LH7 (manure), LL2 (biodynamic plots), LH1 (livestock manure)	Ecoinvent leaching fractions represent European averages; Mediterranean and boreal conditions may differ	MODERATE
TA (kg SO₂-eq)	Diesel consumption from field surveys; Ecoinvent combustion emission factors	All LHs & LLs with significant machinery use	Well-characterised process; low sensitivity to fuel consumption estimates	LOW
SOD (kg CFC11-eq)	Dominated by fuel combustion; robustly characterised in Ecoinvent	All LHs & LLs	Results robust across all case studies; differences between systems negligible	LOW

3. Integrated overview of interventions: LCA results and ecosystem services valuation

The environmental impacts quantified in the LCA (sections 2.1–2.4) represent physical burdens (kg of CO₂ eq., kg of SO₂ eq, kg of 1,4-DCB, etc.) that are not directly comparable with the economic costs and benefits of soil management. To enable a coherent cost-benefit assessment, these impacts are translated into monetary units following the approach set out in the *InBestSoil Report on Environmental Cost-Benefit Analysis of Soil Management Practices* (see Annex II attached to this deliverable).

The monetisation is based on the environmental prices provided by the Handbook of Environmental Prices by CE Delft (2024), which express the social cost of each unit of pollutant released, that is the loss of economic welfare that society incurs when an additional kilogram of a given substance is emitted. These prices are compatible with the ReCiPe 2016 midpoint framework used in this LCA.

The resulting environmental costs (€/ha/yr) are combined with market revenues and non-market ecosystem service values (**D3.2 - Economic valuation of ecosystem services and disservices in LH**) to derive the social margin of each intervention, the net benefit to society of investing in soil health.

Table 17. Integrated overview of soil management interventions and socio-economic results per case study.

Case Study	Main Intervention	LCA Results (Monetised Environmental Costs)	Economic Results (Net Social Margin)
LH1	Transition to regenerative rotational grazing with native breeds	354€/ha: 99% of the impact comes from livestock emissions and feed	17,138€/ha/year: Cultural and regulating service benefits offset operational costs
LH2	Restoration of mining soils using Technosols and phytostabilization	2.62€/ha/year: Main impact occurs during the initial application phase	22,744€/ha/year: Massive improvement in supporting services and reduced metal mobility
LH3	Remediation of copper mine using organic-based Technosols	75.16€/ha/year: Hotspots are Technosol production and transport	32,242€/ha/year: Highest increase in net social value due to soil function recovery
LH4	Sustainable practices: mulching, low disturbance, and grasslands	344 €/ha (annual cropland); 438€/ha (apple orchard): Fertilizer use is the dominant burden	4,145€/ha/year: High-value production absorbs externalities
LH5	Sustainable urban agriculture (composting, no-till, no chemicals)	6€/ha: Minimal environmental impact compared to conventional systems	32,275€/ha/year: Social value driven by community benefits and local provisioning

LH6	Shift to sustainable forest management and quarry reforestation	15.61€/ha/year: Low burdens, mainly from initial mechanical	201€/ha/year: Despite negative short-term market margin, social value is positive
LH7	Regenerative management: lupin, diversification, reduced fertilizers	recultivation 467€/ha: 33% reduction in environmental costs vs. conventional system	7.457€/ha/year: Simultaneous improvement in private margin and regulating services
LL1	Conservation agriculture: conventional tillage, reduced tillage and direct seeding (sod-seeding)	€205/ha (sod-seeding): Lowest environmental impact among all practices evaluated	<i>An integrated economic balance for LL1 could not be performed due to inconsistencies between the LCA inventory and the economic datasets provided in D3.2.</i>
LL2	Transition from mineral fertilization to biodynamic systems	Biodynamic (652–1,578€/ha); Conventional (117–1,440€/ha): High impact due to intensive machinery use for organic inputs	<i>Non-market ecosystem services are not accounted for due to data limitations.</i>

Across all nine living labs, the e-CBA consistently demonstrates that sustainable soil management generates positive net social value, even when market returns are negative or limited. Environmental costs range from negligible (6 €/ha in LH5) to substantial (438 €/ha in LH4), yet wherever ecosystem services could be fully valued, the social margin is positive. This pattern holds across radically different soil types, climates, and intervention strategies, reinforcing the e-CBA framework as a robust decision-support tool for soil policy.

Industrial soils

Both technosol-based remediation interventions achieve among the highest social margins despite being the most capital-intensive cases. In **LH2**, once annualised over 68 years, environmental costs fall to just 2.62 €/ha/year, and ecosystem service gains yield a social margin of +22,744 €/ha/year. In **LH3**, annualised environmental costs reach 75 €/ha/year (4% of total costs), yet ecosystem service recovery delivers the highest absolute social margin in the entire analysis at +32,242 €/ha/year.

Urban soils

In **LH4**, the apple orchard under sustainable management achieves a social margin of +18,598 €/ha/year, while grassland management reduces environmental costs by 91% compared to conventional cropland. In **LH5**, urban gardening stands out as the lowest-impact intervention across all living labs (6 €/ha in environmental costs), with a social margin of +32,275 €/ha/year almost entirely driven by ecosystem services, reflecting the broad community and regulating benefits of urban green infrastructure.

Agricultural soils

In **LH7**, organic management delivers a clear social margin gain of +7,457 €/ha/year over conventional, driven by higher ecosystem services, greater revenues, and a 33% reduction in environmental costs. In **LL1**, sod seeding reduces environmental costs by 27%, though data inconsistencies prevented a full economic comparison. In **LL2**, only biodynamic lentils and conventional fodder achieve positive social margins when ecosystem services are excluded, though the true value of biodynamic practices is likely substantially underestimated due to this data limitation.

Forestry soils

Both forestry interventions show negative market balances but strongly positive social outcomes. In **LH1**, rotational grazing with native breeds yields an outstanding social margin of +17,138 €/ha/year, driven by the recovery of regulating and cultural ecosystem services, despite high environmental costs from livestock emissions (354 €/ha/year). In **LH6**, sustainable boreal forest management generates zero market revenues yet achieves a positive social margin of +201 €/ha/year, with annualised environmental costs of just 15.61 €/ha/year.

Environmental costs represent between 3% and 58% of total land management costs, and their omission from conventional assessments leads to systematically distorted conclusions. Conventional practices that appear financially viable in market terms frequently generate net social losses once externalities are internalised, while high-investment restoration proves socially efficient when ecosystem services are fully valued. Across all land use types, ecosystem services — not market revenues — are the decisive factor in social performance, underscoring the need for public policy instruments that reward non-market benefits to align private incentives with societal goals.

4. Conclusions

The results obtained from the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) conducted across the various case studies (Lighthouses and Living Labs) within the InBestSoil project allow for the extraction of several key conclusions regarding the environmental performance of soil health improvement practices.

Firstly, it has been demonstrated that sustainable soil management practices—such as regenerative and biodynamic agriculture, direct seeding, organic matter incorporation, rotational grazing, and reforestation—tend to show lower environmental impacts compared to conventional approaches. These interventions have proven effective in reducing greenhouse gas emissions, improving resource efficiency, and limiting toxicity-related impacts across diverse soil types and regions.

The integration of LCA methodology has enabled a robust comparative assessment of practices across agricultural, forestry, urban, and industrial soils, covering several biogeographic regions in Europe. The main findings indicate that:

- In **agricultural systems**, regenerative and biodynamic practices significantly reduce global warming potential (GWP) supporting more climate-resilient farming models. Direct seeding substantially reduces the environmental impacts associated with tillage and soil disturbance, contributing to energy savings and a more favourable carbon balance.

- In **forestry contexts**, sustainable soil management improves soil health and ecosystem function, but carries environmental trade-offs. Rotational grazing supports soil quality and biodiversity, yet livestock and feed production contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions and soil toxicity. Reforestation and careful soil management restore degraded soils, but machinery use, seedling production, and liming drive energy use and CO₂ emissions. Overall, sustainable restoration enhances soil quality and resilience but requires balancing ecological benefits with the environmental impacts of management practices.
- In **urban and industrial soils**, active rehabilitation using amendments, technosols, and revegetation strategies provides environmental benefits, though with results that vary depending on the specific materials and techniques applied.

Moreover, the use of LCA has proven effective in identifying the processes with the highest environmental burdens within each system, allowing decision-makers to prioritize more sustainable interventions. Adapting practices to local environmental, climatic, and socio-economic conditions is essential to maximize effectiveness and reduce trade-offs.

5. References

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ANNEX I: Inventory data

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LH2
TYPE OF SOIL	Technosol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	1,5	ha

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	NA	NA	
	NA	NA	
	NA	NA	

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product:
(e.g. Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you deem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
31/01/2011	Tillage	Combined machine consisting of a classic subsoiler, a fast harrow and a compactation roller.		Breakage of soil compaction	5150	m ³					2	16	10	
31/01/2011	Surface levelling	Laser leveling machine		Channelling runoff	14095	m ²					2	12	6	
	Application of marble waste	Truck+tractor+slurry tank	waste from the marble extraction (pure calcium carbonate)	Creation of Technosol	95000	kg					3	6	5	
	Application of pig slurry	Truck+tractor+spreader trailer	Pig slurry from farm	Creation of Technosol	60	m ³					3	6	5	
	Application of manure	Truck+tractor+spreader trailer	Manure from pig farm	Creation of Technosol	24000	kg					3	6	5	
01/03/2012	Plantation	Manual	Atriplex halimus, Tamarix canariensis, Pistacea lentiscus, Tetraclinis articulata, Chamaerops humilis, Lavandula dentata, Salvia rosmarinus, Cistus albidus, Helichrysum decumbens, Hyparrhenia hirta, Limonium cossonianum, Lygeum spartum, Phagnalon saxatile	Creation of a native vegetation cover	14000	plants/ha					7	manual	16	
01/03/2012	Sowing	Manual	Cynodon dactylon, Dittrichia viscosa, Piptatherum milaceum, Sonchus tenerrimus, Zygodophyllum fabago, Atriplex halimus, Cistus albidus, Helichrysum decumbens, Phagnalon saxatile	Creation of a native vegetation cover	18000	plants/ha					7	manual	6	
01/03/2012	Irrigation		Regenerated water from wastewater treatment plant	Survival of plants			200	m ³	applied with vat		4	manual	6	

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LH41
TYPE OF SOIL	Pseudogley and fluvisol

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product:
(e.g. Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivative (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	1	ha

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	apple	21	ton

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
31.10.2023.	Fertilizer application	Tractor (45kW) + fertilizer spreader (600 kg capacity)	NPK (7-20-30) fertilizer	nutrient deficit in soil	200	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	7		
09.01.2024.	Pesticide application	Motorised Backpack Sprayers	Fungicide	crop protection	1,8	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	0	8	CUPRABLAU Z 35 WG
14.03.2024.	Pesticide application	Motorised Backpack Sprayers	Fungicide	crop protection	1,8	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	0	8	CUPRABLAU Z 35 WG
23.03.2024.	Pruning	AKU hand tool	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	0	64	
19.4.2024.	Fertilizer application	Tractor (45kW) + fertilizer spreader (600 kg capacity)	KAN (27N) fertilizer	nutrient deficit in soil	100	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	6		
20.04.2024.	Mulching	Tractor (45kW) + mulcher	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2		
31.4.2024	Fertilizer application	Tractor (45kW) + sprayer (1200L capacity)	KAN (27% N) fertilizer	for crop growth	100	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	9		
02.05.2024.	Pesticide application	Motorised Backpack Sprayers	Fungicide	crop protection	2	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	0	8	TERCEL
19.06.2024.	Mulching	Tractor (45kW) + mulcher	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2		
02.07.2024.	Pesticide application	Motorised Backpack Sprayers	Fungicide	crop protection	2	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	0	8	TERCEL
31.07.2024.	Pesticide application	Motorised Backpack Sprayers	Fungicide	crop protection	2	0,2 kg/ha + 0,6 kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	0	8	Stroby® WG + Delan® 700 WDG
03.9.2024.	Harvest	Tractor (45kw) + trailer (5t capacity)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	5	8	26	
16.9.2024.	Transportation	Forklift + truck with a trailer	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	9	

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LH42
TYPE OF SOIL	Pseudogley and fluvisol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	1	ha

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	-		

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product:
(e.g: Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
20.04.2024.	Mulching	Tractor (45kW) + mulcher	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2		
19.06.2024.	Mulching	Tractor (45kW) + mulcher	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2		
31.09.2024.	Mulching	Tractor (45kW) + mulcher	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	2		

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LH45
TYPE OF SOIL	Pseudogley and fluvisol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	17	ha

	PRODUCT¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	winter wheat (grain)	85	ton
	winter wheat (straw)	136	ton

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible (e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product: (e.g: Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	COMMENTS ¹¹
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ² , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)		
20.10.2023.	Ploughing	Tractor (120kW) + 3 furrow mounted plough	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	26		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
25.10.2023.	Harrowing	Tractor (120kW) + rotary harrow (3m width)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	24		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
28.10.2023.	Fertilizer application	Tractor (93kW) + fertilizer spreader (600 kg capacity)	NPK (7-20-30) fertilizer	nutrient deficit in soil	500	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	9		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
30.10.2023	Harrowing	Tractor (120kW) + rotary harrow (3m width)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	24		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
3.11.2023.	Sowing	Tractor (93kW) + pneumatic seed drill (4m width)	seed of winter wheat	for sowing	250	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	20		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
31.1.2024	Fertilizer application	Tractor (93kW) + sprayer (1200L capacity)	KAN (27% N) fertilizer	for crop growth	100	kg/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	9		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
20.3.2024.	Pesticide application	Tractor (93kW) + sprayer (1200L capacity)	Herbicide	crop protection	1 and 300	L/ha and g/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	9		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	two types of herbicide were used, Axial 50 EC (1L/ha) by Syngenta composed out of Pinoxaden, and the other one is Hussar OD (300 g/ha) by Bayer Crop Science composed out of Iodosulfuron
29.4.2024.	Pesticide application	Tractor (93kW) + sprayer (1200L capacity)	Fungicide	crop protection	1	L/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	9		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	Used compound is Prothioconazole and Tebuconazole or the market name of the product is Prosaro 250 EC by Bayer crop Science
19.6.2024.	Liquid fertilizer application	Tractor (93kW) + sprayer (1200L capacity)	NPK (30-10-10) fertilizer	foliar feed for crop	5	L/ha	NA	NA	NA	NA	1	9		Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
15.7.2024.	Harvest	Harvester (160kW) + tractor(120kW)+ tractor (93kw) + 2 two-axel trailers (8t capacity)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	3	60	30	Driving hours are not per 1ha, while per 17ha	
30.7.2024.	Loading	Forklift + truck with a trailer	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	2	1	9	Hours are only for loading the truck	

IDENTIFICATION	farm
TYPE OF SOIL	anthrosol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	1	0,5

	PRODUCT¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	Beetroot	12	kg
	Carrots	8	kg
	Beans	1,5	kg
	Tomatoes	50	kg
	Cucumbers	15	kg
	Potatoes	70	kg
	Onions	15	kg
	Strawberries	10	kg
	Garlic	2	kg
Zuchini	20	kg	

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible (e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product: (e.g: Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL			IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)		TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)
2024 April-October	Plantings	Honda grass cutting machine (horsepower 4) only for cutting glass	Seeds for tomatoes		10	kg	150	m3	None	None	2	Grass cutting machine	144	12 times
	Weeding the beds		Seeds for cucumbers		0,002	kg								
	Irrigating		Seeds for potatoes		0,002	kg								
	Harvesting		Seeds for beetroot		0,002	kg								
			Seeds for carrots		0,002	kg								
			Seeds for beans		0,002	kg								
			Seeds for onions		0,002	kg								
			Seeds for strawberries		0,002	kg								
			Seeds for garlic		0,002	kg								
			Seeds for zuchini		0,002	kg								
	Fertilization													

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LH6
TYPE OF SOIL	Sand (quarry)

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	6,225	ha

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION			

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities.
If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
01.04.2023.	Quarry restoration plan	Paperwork									1			7500 EUR
30.11.2023.	Recultivation	tractor+excavator									3	40	42	total area 6.225ha, 17030.50EUR
19.04.2024.	Seedlings	(Pinus sylvestris, Picea abies, Betula pendula, Alnus glutinosa)			1340	number								
19.04.2024.	Planting	manual (shovel and planting barrel)			465	plants/ha					25	manual	3	
15.05.2024.	Soil conditioning	Manual spreading	Different soil conditioning material		0,7	kg/plant					2	manual		4 ~ 20EUR/h
08.08.2024.	Agro-technical care	trimmer									2	3	3	329.00 EUR/ha
15.09.2024.	Protection of the generations	sprayer	repelent Trico		10	l/ha					6	7	8	129.00 EUR/ha

CONVENTIONAL FARM
Income

					1 hectare		
Description	Quantity	Unit	Price per Unit (€)	Total Amount (€)		ECONOMIC ALLOCATION	
Main product	9000 kg	€	0,24	€ 2.160,00		90%	
Straw	4800 kg	€	0,07	€ 253,00		10%	
Gross revenue (a)				€ 2.413,00			

Costs

Description	Quantity	Unit	Price per Unit (€)	Total Amount (€)
Inputs -seed				
winter barley normal seed + fungicides	160 kg	€	0,65	€ 104,00
Fertilisation				
Calcium ammonium nitrate 27% N	140 kg N	€	0,82	€ 114,80
Pest management				
Diflufenican 200, flufunaet 400	0,5 kg,l	€	97,00	€ 48,50
Fluroxypyr-meptyl (333)	0,45 kg,l	€	50,00	€ 22,50
cyprodinil (187,5), isopyrazam (62.5)	1,5 kg,l	€	34,00	€ 51,00
rinexapac-ethyl (250)	0,8 kg,l	€	52,00	€ 41,60
Bixafen (75), prothioconazole (100), tebuconazole (100)	1 kg,l	€	62,00	€ 62,00
Vegetable oil	1 kg,l	€	4,00	€ 4,00
Metsulfuron-methyl (40), bensulfuron-methyl (500)	0,1 kg,l	€	191,00	€ 19,10
Fuel				
Diesel	133,52 liters	€	1,18	€ 158,00
Other costs				
Calculated interest	124,59 EUR	€	0,03	€ -
N-mineral sample	0,5 times	€	36,25	€ 18,00
Drying barley	7,5 tons	€	3,75	€ 28,00
Handling costs for wheat and barley	7,5 tons	€	10,00	€ 75,00
Land rental	1 ha	€	620,00	€ 620,00
All activities.				
Soil preparation	4,3 hours		80	€ 344,00
Fertilizing	0,6 hours		90	€ 54,00
Sowing/planting	0,9 hours		80	€ 72,00
Crop protection	1,3 hours		75	€ 97,50
Harvesting	3,1 hours		120	€ 372,00
Gross costs				€ 2.306,00
Balance/ha	10,2			€ 107,00

ORGANIC FARM**Income**

Area:

6

Description	Quantity	Unit	ce per Unit	Price unit	Total Amount (€)	ECONOMIC ALLOCATION
main product	1500 kg			0,6 €/kg	5400	93%
straw 1)	1000 kg			0,07 €/kg	420	7%
Gross revenue					5820	

Costs

Description	Quantity	Unit	ce per Unit	Price unit	Total Amount (€)
Seeds					
Winterbarley organic	140 kg/ha			0,83 €/kg	697,2
Spring barley (reseeding)	24 kg/ha			0,83 €/kg	119,52
Green manure	50 kg/ha			3 €/kg	900
Fertilisation					
Straw manure organic	8 m3/ha			10 €/m3	480
Fuel					
diesel	76,45 liter/ha			1,18 €/l	541
Other costs					
calculated interest	152,58 EUR/ha			0,03 %	0
drying barley	5 ton/ha			3,75 €/ton	112,5
Land rental	1 ha			620	3720
Activities					
Seeding green manure	4 hour			80 €	320
Eco-ploughing	4 hour			80 €	320
Manuring, manure spreader (Fall 2023)	7 hour			120 €	840
Seeding (Fall 2023)	4 hour			80 €	320
Soil preparation + weeding	14 hour			80 €	1120
Reseeding (part of the crop failed due to t	2 hour			80 €	160
Combining (harvest)	4 hour			120 €	480
Total costs					10130

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL1 - LH1 Ussana
TYPE OF SOIL	LUVISOL -

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	1	ha

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION			

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible (e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product: (e.g. Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

Treatments

Conventional tillage 1.293

Reduced tillage 1.091

Sod seeding 1.748

grain yield (ton/ha)

all values (operation and yield) are per hectare

Conventional tillage

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)		
20/11/2023	Ploughing	JD 5090 (90 hp) + mouldboard plough (Nardi POP 90)	tillage (30 cm depth)	seedbed preparation				no irrigation				1	2,7	0	
12/12/2023	Harrowing	CLAAS AXION 810 (215hp) + disc harrows (Maschio veloce 50 pp - 5m)	tillage (12 cm depth)	seedbed preparation								1	0,4	0	
14/12/2023	sowing	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	seeds	planting	195							2	0,85	0,85	Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
14/12/2023	fertilization	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	fertilizer	fertilization	200										Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
18/12/2023	soil rolling	roller (3m)										1	0,4		
08/02/2024	fertilization	JD5820 (65kW) + Amazone ZA-V Tronic	fertilizer (Urea - 46)	fertilization	100 kg							2	0,12	0,12	
14/03/2024	weeding	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Hardy (12m)	erbicide	weeding	1 l/ha Timeline TRIO + 0.5 l/ha Axial Pronto 60 (300 l/ha solution)							1	0,3	0	
04/07/2024	harvest	WINTERSTEIGER Delta plot combine	harvest sampling	grain harvest											only sampling of grain for determining yield and grain quality
10/07/2024	harvest	CLAAS Dominator maxi 88SL (115 kW; width 4.5 m)	harvest	grain harvest and shredding wheat straw								1	0,7		ordinary harvest

Reduced tillage

								no irrigation							
12/12/2023	weeding	JD5820 (65kW) + Caffini (18m)	herbicides	weeding	3l/ha glyphosate + 3 kg ammonium sulphate							1	0,25	0	3l/ha glyphosate + 1 kg/100 l ammonium sulphate (distribution of 300l/ha)
12/12/2023	Harrowing	CLAAS AXION 810 (215hp) + disc harrows (Maschio veloce 50 pp - 5m)	tillage (12 cm depth)	seedbed preparation								1	0,4	0	
14/12/2023	sowing	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	seeds	planting	195							2	0,85	0,85	Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
14/12/2023	fertilization	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	fertilizer	fertilization	200										Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
18/12/2023	soil rolling	roller (3m)										1	0,4		
08/02/2024	fertilization	JD5820 (65kW) + Amazone ZA-V Tronic	fertilizer (Urea - 46)	fertilization	100 kg							2	0,12	0,12	
14/03/2024	weeding	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Hardy (12m)	erbicide	weeding	0.5 l/ha Axial Pronto 60 (300 l/ha solution)							1	0,3	0	
04/07/2024	harvest	WINTERSTEIGER Delta plot combine	harvest sampling	grain harvest											only sampling of grain for determining yield and grain quality

10/07/2024	harvest	CLAAS Dominator maxi 88SL (115 kW; width 4.5 m)	harvest	grain harvest and shredding wheat straw							1	0,7		ordinary harvest
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Sod seeding															
															no irrigation
12/12/2023	weeding	JD5820 (65kW) + Caffini (18m)	herbicides	weeding	3l/ha glyphosate + 3 kg ammonium sulphate							1	0,25		3l/ha glyphosate + 1 kg/100 l ammonium sulphate (distribution of 300l/ha)
14/12/2023	sowing	JD5820 (65hp) + Semeato SHM 11/13 (2.5 m)	seeds	planting	195							2	0,9	0,9	Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
14/12/2023	fertilization	JD5820 (65hp) + Semeato SHM 11/13 (2.5 m)	fertilizer	fertilization	200										Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
18/12/2023	soil rolling	roller (3m)										1	0,4		
08/02/2024	fertilization	JD5820 (65kW) + Amazone ZA-V Tronic	fertilizer (Urea - 46)	fertilization	100 kg							2	0,12	0,12	
14/03/2024	weeding	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Hardy (12m)	erbicide	weeding	1 l/ha Timeline TRIO + 0.5 l/ha Axial Pronto 60 (300 l/ha solution)							1	0,3	0	
04/07/2024	harvest	WINTERSTEIGER Delta plot combine	harvest sampling	grain harvest											only sampling of grain for determining yield and grain quality
10/07/2024	harvest	CLAAS Dominator maxi 88SL (115 kW; width 4.5 m)	harvest	grain harvest and shredding wheat straw								1	0,7		ordinary harvest

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL1 - LH2 Benatzu
TYPE OF SOIL	Cambisol

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product:
(e.g. Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	1	ha

Location: 39.41038 N, 9.09052 E

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION			

Treatments

Treatments	grain yield (ton/ha)
Conventional tillage	1.214
Reduced tillage	1.398
Sod seeding	2.282

all values (operation and yield) are per hectare

Conventional tillage

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)		
12/12/2023	Ploughing	JD 5090 (90 hp) + mouldboard plough (Nardi POP 90)	tillage (30 cm depth)	seedbed preparation		cm						1	2,7	0	
13/12/2023	Harrowing	CLAAS AXION 810 (215hp) + disc harrows (Maschio veloce 50 pp - 5m)	tillage (12 cm depth)	seedbed preparation		cm						1	0,4	0	
15/12/2023	sowing	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	seeds	planting		195 kg						2	0,85	0,85	Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
15/12/2023	fertilization	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	fertilizer	fertilization		200 kg									Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
18/12/2023	soil rolling	roller (3m)										1	0,4		
08/02/2024	fertilization	JD5820 (65kW) + Amazone ZA-V Tronic	fertilizer (Urea - 46)	fertilization		100 kg						2	0,12	0,12	
14/03/2024	weeding	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Hardy (12m)	erbicide	weeding		1 l/ha Timeline TRIO + 0.5 l/ha Axial Pronto 60 (300 l/ha solution)	l					1	0,3	0	
04/07/2024	harvest	WINTERSTEIGER Delta plot combine	harvest sampling	grain harvest											only sampling of grain for determining yield and grain quality
10/07/2024	harvest	CLAAS Dominator maxi 88SL (115 kW; width 4.5 m)	harvest	grain harvest and shredding wheat straw								1	0,7		ordinary harvest

Reduced tillage

12/12/2023	weeding	JD5820 (65kW) + Caffini (18m)	herbicides	weeding		3l/ha glyphosate + 3 kg ammonium sulphate	l					1	0,25	0	3l/ha glyphosate + 1 kg/100 l ammonium sulphate (distribution of 300l/ha)
12/12/2023	Harrowing	CLAAS AXION 810 (215hp) + disc harrows (Maschio veloce 50 pp - 5m)	tillage (12 cm depth)	seedbed preparation								1	0,4	0	
14/12/2023	sowing	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	seeds	planting		195 kg						2	0,85	0,85	Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
14/12/2023	fertilization	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Gaspardo SLC 250 (2.5 m)	fertilizer	fertilization		200 kg									Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
18/12/2023	soil rolling	roller (3m)										1	0,4		
08/02/2024	fertilization	JD 5820 (65 kW) + Amazone ZA-V Tronic	fertilizer (Urea - 46)	fertilization		100 kg						2	0,12	0,12	

14/03/2024	weeding	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Hardy (12m)	erbicide	weeding	1 l/ha Timeline TRIO + 0.5 l/ha Axial Pronto 60 (300 l/ha solution)	l						1	0,3	0	
04/07/2024	harvest	WINTERSTEIGER Delta plot combine	harvest sampling	grain harvest											only sampling of grain for determining yield and grain quality
10/07/2024	harvest	CLAAS Dominator maxi 88SL (115 kW; width 4.5 m)	harvest	grain harvest and shredding wheat straw								1	0,7		ordinary harvest

Sod Seeding

12/12/2023	weeding	JD5820 (65kW) + Caffini (18m)	herbicides	weeding	3l/ha glyphosate + 3 kg ammonium sulphate	l						1	0,25	0	3l/ha glyphosate + 1 kg/100 l ammonium sulphate (distribution of 300l/ha)
14/12/2023	sowing	JD5820 (65hp) + Semeato SHM 11/13 (2.5 m)	seeds	planting	195 kg	kg						2	0,9	0,9	Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
14/12/2023	fertilization	JD5820 (65hp) + Semeato SHM 11/13 (2.5 m)	fertilizer	fertilization	200 kg	kg									Sowing and fertilization with the same operation
18/12/2023	soil rolling	roller (3m)										1	0,4		
08/02/2024	fertilization	JD 5820 (65 kW) + Amazone ZA-V Tronic	fertilizer (Urea - 46)	fertilization	100 kg	kg						2	0,12	0,12	
14/03/2024	weeding	New Holland TN65D (65hp) + Hardy (12m)	erbicide	weeding	1 l/ha Timeline TRIO + 0.5 l/ha Axial Pronto 60 (300 l/ha solution)	l						1	0,3	0	
04/07/2024	harvest	WINTERSTEIGER Delta plot combine	harvest sampling	grain harvest											only sampling of grain for determining yield and grain quality
10/07/2024	harvest	CLAAS Dominator maxi 88SL (115 kW; width 4.5 m)	harvest	grain harvest and shredding wheat straw								1	0,7		ordinary harvest

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL2: LL1-LL3
TYPE OF SOIL	stoney Cambisol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	20000	m ²

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	Faba bean	7120	kg
	Triticale	2030	kg

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product:
(e.g: Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)		
30/09/2023	Mulching	John Deere 6120 120hp + mulcher 3m	Mulch	incorporation of cover crop			no irrigation at all					1	4	1	
30/09/2023	Stubble ploughing (6cm depth)	John Deere 6120 120hp + stubble plough 4 mouldboards	Stubble plowing	tillage								1	6	0,5	
22/10/2023	Sowing of faba bean and Triticale	John Deere 6120 120hp + Seeddrill combination (with rotary harrow) 3m	Seeds	Sowing of crops	90 Beans and 80kg Triticcal	kg						1	6	1	
01/10/2023	Fertilization	John Deere 6120 120hp + Manure Spreader	Fertiliser (Bokkashi)	start fertilisation	60	m3						1	3	1	
15/02/2024	Fertilization	John Deere 6120 120hp + Spreader	Fertiliser(elemental sulfur 90%)	soil health, effect on nutrients and fungi	160	kg						1	2	1	
29/02/2024	Fertilization	John Deere 6120 120hp + Spreader	Kieserit (15% Mg (ESTA Kieserite)	plant health and need; organic fertilisation	330	kg						1	2	1	
22/03/2024	Compost Tea application 100l/ha	John Deere 6120 120hp + Sprayer	Compost Tea with EM	activate soil live and improve plant health	200	liters						1	1	1	
24/07/2024	Harvest	Claas Evion 400 230Hp	Grains and Beans	Harvest of crop	9150	kg						2	5	2	

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL2: LL4-LL6	
TYPE OF SOIL	stoney Cambisol	
	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	12800	m ²

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	Mountainlentils + naked oats	2500	kg

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
07/04/2024	Stubble ploughing (6cm depth)	John Deere 6120 120hp + stubble plough 4 mouldboards	Stubble plowing	tillage		2					1	3	1	
12/04/2024	Wing cultivation (flat)	John Deere 6120 120hp + wing cultivator 3m	Cultivation	seedbed preparation							1	2	1	
14/04/2024	Sowing	John Deere 6120 120hp + Seeddrill combination (with rotary harrow) 3m	Seeds	Cropping	115	kg/ha					1	2	1	
29/02/2024	Fertilization	John Deere 6120 120hp + Spreader	Fertiliser(elemental sulfur 90%)	soil health, effect on nutrients and fungi	76,8	kg					1	1	1	
29/02/2024	Fertilization	John Deere 6120 120hp + Spreader	Kieserit (15% Mg (ESTA Kieserite)	plant health and need; organic fertilisation	211	kg					1	1	0,5	
13/05/2024	Mechanic weed control	John Deere 6120 120hp + tined weeder									1	1	0,5	
07/06/2024	Effective Microorganisms	John Deere 6120 120hp + Sprayer	Horn Manure and Horn Chiesel		n.n						1	1	0,25	
10/08/2024	Harvest	Claas Evion 400 230Hp	Lentils and naked oats		2500	kg					2	4	1	
16/08/2024	Sowing of cover Crop	John Deere 6120 120hp + direct seed drill	Cover crop mixture		n.n									

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL2: LL7-LL9
TYPE OF SOIL	stoney Cambisol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	3169	m ²

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	extended flowering cover crop	nectare for bees and other insects	n.n
	used as transfer mulch for potatoes as well	transfer to the other field	n.n

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ⁴	MACHINERY USED ²	TYPE ³	RAW MATERIAL			IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
				REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
28/09/2023	flat subble ploghing	John Deere 6120 120hp + stubble plough 4 mouldboards	Tillage								1	2	0,5	
28/09/2023	Sowing	John Deere 6120 120hp + Seeddrill combination (with rotary harow) 3m	Seeds	Flowering field							1	2	1	
no more works in 2024														

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL2: LL13-LL15	
TYPE OF SOIL	stoney Cambisol	
	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	20692	m ²

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

	PRODUCT¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	Family Labyrinth	biomass stays on the field	kg
	Fun and experience for kids and grown ups	SOM built up	kg
	no harvest of crops		

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	RAW MATERIAL				IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰
			TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)	TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)	
11/05/2024	Surface Composting with ferment liquid	John Deere 6120 120hp + rotary tiller	incorporating plant biomass	preparation for sowing	n.n						1	2	2	
06/06/2024	flat harrowing for seedbed	John Deere 6120 120hp + harrow (2-3cm depth)		seedbed preparation							1	2	0,5	
06/06/2024	sowing for Labyrinth	John Deere 6120 120hp + Seeddrill combination (with rotary harrow) 3m	seeds per ha: (30kg hemp, 50kg faba beans, 5kg millet, 10kg GCF, 2kg Soblu, 5kg Solanum Pro	Labyrinth	500	kg					1	4	2	
13/06/2024	Fertilisation	John Deere 6120 120hp + Spreader	Fertiliser Biorga N pellets	Nitrogen for better growth and C:N ratio	1035	kg					1	2	1	
07/06/2024	Fertilisation	John Deere 6120 120hp + Spreader	Horn manure and Horn Chiesel	Microorganisms	n.n	kg					1	2	1	

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL2: LL19-LL21
TYPE OF SOIL	Cambisol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	29500	m ²

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	Hay and Silage	32100	kg

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible
(e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product:
(e.g: Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	RAW MATERIAL		IRRIGATION			WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	
					AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)		TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)
15/02/2024	Slurry Fertilization	Steyr CVT 6175 + Zunhammer K12.5PUL with spreading boom	organic fertilizer	soil organisms, SOM, grass growth, slurry storage	58,94	m ³					1	6	0,5	
09/05/2024	Grass mowing for hay	Steyr CVT 6175 + Kuhn Mower 8831 and 3221	grass for hayballs	fodder	14800	kg					1	3	0,5	data in between grass mowing and hay pressing is missing
15/05/2024	Slurry Fertilization	Steyr CVT 6175 + Zunhammer K12.5PUL with spreading boom	organic fertilizer	soil organisms, SOM, grass growth, slurry storage	58,94	m ³					1	6	2	
16/06/2024	Grass mowing for silage	Steyr CVT 6175 + Kuhn Mower 8831 and 3221	grass for silage	fodder	7350	kg					1	3	3	data of steps until harvest are missing
20/06/2024	Slurry Fertilization	Steyr CVT 6175 + Zunhammer K12.5PUL with spreading boom	organic fertilizer	soil organisms, SOM, grass growth, slurry storage	58,94	m ³					1	6	0,5	

LIGHTHOUSE IDENTIFICATION	LL2: LL22-LL24
TYPE OF SOIL	Cambisol

	AMOUNT	Units (ha, m ²)
TOTAL OPERATION SURFACE	10200	m ²

	PRODUCT ¹¹	AMOUNT OF PRODUCT ¹²	Units (kg, ton)
TOTAL PRODUCTION	Milling Wheat	15301,7	kg

1: Activity Performed (e.g. Grazing, Mulching, Sowing)
Give a short description of the activity if need in the comments section

2: Machinery used during the process. Specify as much as possible (e.g. Tractor 100 Hp + Arado de Grada)

3) Seeds, Fertilizers, Herbicides, Pesticides, etc., indicating the type of compound used

4) Explain the precise motive for the application of the product: (e.g: Pest control, lack of resources, etc.)

5: Amount of water used for irrigation/or activities on which water is used

6: Electricity consumed during the activities placed on water amount

7: All the workers, including the machinery operator

8: Driving hours of the machinery during the activities. If the machinery needs to be moved, consider that another work

9: Do not take into account here the working hours of the machinery operator

10: Include any information you seem valuable for the understanding of the process

11: Consider all the products extracted from the soil or produced as a derivate (Harvested products, meat production, etc)

12: In time of the process

OPERATION DATE	PERFORMED WORK ¹	MACHINERY USED ²	Notas (Ana)	RAW MATERIAL			IRRIGATION				WORK DURATION			COMMENTS ¹⁰	
				TYPE ³	REASON FOR USE ⁴	AMOUNT	Units (kg, L, m ³ number)	WATER AMOUNT ⁵	Units (m ³ , L, kg)	ELECTRICITY CONSUMPTION IN IRRIGATION ⁶	Units (kW-h, W-h)	NUMBER OF WORKERS/ OPERATORS ⁷	MACHINERY USAGE TIME ⁸ (Driving hours)		TOTAL WORKING HOURS ⁹ (Working time of all workers except the driver)
08/10/2023	corn stubble mulching	Steyr CVT 6175 + mucher front and heck	Steyr CVT 6175 --> 175hp	corn borer protection	regulate corn borer habitat and increase decomposition of lignin rich stubbles	field residues						1	2	0,5	
11/10/2023	organic fertilization	Steyr CVT 6175 + manure spreader JF		organic fertilizer	SOM and soil organisms, humus built up	20390	kg					1	12	1	
12/10/2023	Plowing	Steyr CVT 6270 Terrus + Kuhn 5 plates plow	Steyr CVT 6270 --> 270hp	tillage	conventional tillage after corn							1	6	0,5	
12/10/2023	Sowing 4cm depth	Steyr CVT 6175 + Kverneland 3m + Knoche Roller	350 granos/m ² × 0.04 g/grano = 14 g/m ² APROX	seeds	sowing wheat	350grains	m ²					1	4	1	
01/11/2023	Spraying	Case ICH Farmall 95 + Holder Sprayer		Herbicides (Trade names:Miranda, Pengergetic VW/WW)	weed control	1,32	liter					1	2	1	
29/02/2024	Fertilization	Weidemann Hoftrac + Case ICH Farmall 95 + Rauch fertilizer spreader		mineral fertilizer: ASS 21N 3Mg 15S	plant growth and stocking	48,09	kg					1	1	0,5	
27/03/2024	Fertilization	Weidemann Hoftrac + Case ICH Farmall 95 + Rauch fertilizer spreader		mineral fertilizer: 46% N Urea	plant growth and stocking	46,92	kg					1	1	0,5	
30/04/2024	Fertilization	Weidemann Hoftrac + Case ICH Farmall 95 + Rauch fertilizer spreader		mineral fertilizer: 46% N Urea	plant growth and sprouting	46,92	kg					1	1	0,5	

ANNEX II: Report on environmental cost-benefit analysis of the soil management practices

InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil

REPORT ON ENVIRONMENTAL COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF THE SOIL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Prepared by:

University of Vigo (UVIGO) – GEN Research Group
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Glossary of key terms

CBA (Cost-Benefit Analysis): An analytical tool used to support decision-making by comparing the benefits (increases in well-being) and costs (decreases in well-being) of different options in monetary terms. In this report, an environmental CBA (e-CBA) framework is applied to internalise environmental externalities within the economic balance.

Externalities: Environmental and social impacts (positive or negative) resulting from soil management that are not reflected in conventional market prices. In this report, negative externalities are quantified as environmental costs, while positive ones are considered as ecosystem services.

Internalisation of Externalities: The process of incorporating environmental costs and ecosystem service values into economic assessments to ensure these reflect the full social impact of interventions.

Cradle-to-gate approach: A Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) scope that covers the entire value chain, including raw material extraction, the production of external inputs (e.g., fertilizers, machinery), and transport to the site. It excludes use and end-of-life stages. This approach ensures that environmental costs include impacts occurring at a global scale, which often take place very far from the physical boundaries of the managed or restored area (upstream impacts).

Willingness to Pay (WTP): The maximum amount an individual is willing to pay to avoid a negative environmental impact or to secure an environmental benefit. It is the standard economic measure used to capture the social value of non-market goods and services.

Shadow Prices (Environmental Prices): Monetary values assigned to biophysical impacts that do not have a market price, such as pollutant emissions. They represent the loss of economic welfare for society for every extra unit of impact (e.g., 1 kg of CO₂) released into the environment.

Benefit Transfer: A valuation method that estimates the economic value of environmental impacts by adapting monetary estimates from a previous study (e.g., EU-27 average) to specific new case studies. Rigorous adjustments such as spatial (income-based) and temporal corrections (price inflation) are mandatory to ensure geographical relevance and methodological accuracy.

Purchasing Power Parity (PPP): An economic metric used to adjust GDP per capita for spatial differences in income levels between countries. It ensures that the benefit transfer approach for environmental prices is used according to the local economic context of each case study.

Income Elasticity (β): A coefficient reflecting how willingness to pay for environmental quality changes with income. A value of 0.65 is applied in this study, consistent with environmental valuation literature, to adjust environmental prices spatially and temporally.

Social Margin: The final indicator representing the net social balance of a practice. It is calculated as the sum of the Market Margin (Revenues minus Management Costs) and the Non-market Margin (Ecosystem Services minus Environmental Costs).

Trade-offs: Situations in which the improvement of one dimension of performance (e.g., profitability) results in deterioration of another (e.g., environmental quality). The e-CBA framework makes these trade-offs explicit by expressing all effects in monetary terms.

1. Executive Summary

Purpose

This report is based on the results of the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) integrated within the InBestSoil project, with a particular focus on identifying and quantifying the environmental impacts associated with the different soil management practices. The purpose of this environmental cost-benefit analysis (e-CBA) is to go beyond technical LCA by incorporating a monetary valuation of environmental impacts.

By monetising environmental externalities (calculating environmental costs), this report provides a single metric (€) to evaluate different soil management practices and guide decision-making in a circular bioeconomy context. This approach reveals "hidden" costs typically omitted from conventional economic assessments, enabling the integrated evaluation of environmental performance, economic viability, and social value of different soil management practices within a single analytical framework.

Intended audience

The document was designed for policymakers involved in land-use planning, soil protection, and environmental management at both national and EU levels. It is also relevant for researchers in environmental economics, soil science, sustainability assessment, and agroecology. In addition, the report provides evidence-based insights for land managers and practitioners responsible for agricultural, forestry, urban, or industrial soils who seek to optimize soil health and sustainability outcomes through informed management decisions.

Description of the main activities

The main activity was to integrate two different methodologies, LCA and e-CBA, to translate biophysical environmental impacts into monetary units. To do that, impact data derived from the standardised LCA (D3.3- *Report on LCA for activities developed in order to improve soil health in LHs*, WP3, InBestSoil), based on a functional unit of 1 hectare of managed soil, were monetised using a benefit transfer approach to estimate environmental costs. To do this, the Handbook of Environmental Prices (CE Delft, 2024) was applied, providing midpoint monetary valuation factors fully compatible with the ReCiPe 2016 impact assessment framework.

To ensure geographical and temporal relevance, spatial and temporal adjustments were applied. European average prices (EU-27) from the Handbook of Environmental Prices were adapted to the socioeconomic contexts of Spain, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Italy, the Netherlands, and Switzerland, using GDP per capita in purchasing power parity (PPP). Next, the environmental prices were translated to national current prices, which enables environmental externalities to

be directly compared with the financial costs and benefits of soil management. In addition, a temporal adjustment updated 2021 reference prices to 2024 values, reflecting income growth and changes in the social valuation of environmental protection.

Key results

The integrated e-CBA approach provides a consistent basis to evaluate soil management practices across different soils uses:

- In **agricultural systems** (e.g., LH7), switching to organic and regenerative practices reduced environmental costs by 33%, while also improving financial performance. This demonstrates that sustainable farming can simultaneously lower environmental costs and increase overall socio-economic value.
- In **urban soils** (e.g., LH4), conventional cropland was found to be economically inefficient once its environmental cost was internalised. In contrast, sustainable practices such as grasslands reduced environmental costs by 91%, highlighting that some conventional practices that appear profitable may generate net losses for society.
- The restoration of **mining-contaminated industrial soils** (e.g., LH3) involves high environmental costs, reaching 5,110 €/ha, mainly due to the intensive material and transport requirements. These impacts represent one-time investment costs to remediate historical damage and are justified by the long-term recovery of soil functions and ecosystem services, resulting in a strongly positive Net Social Balance exceeding 25,000 €/ha per year.
- In Mediterranean **forests**, sustainable practices like regenerative grazing (e.g., LH1) were associated with higher environmental costs due to increased management intensity but also generated new economic activities (meat production) and improved soil fertility. This illustrates that higher environmental costs can reflect trade-offs associated with the creation of long-term social and economic benefits.
- Environmental costs accounted for between 20% and 60% of total soil management costs across several LLs/LHs, demonstrating that a substantial share of societal costs is typically omitted from conventional economic assessments.

Research and practice implications

The results demonstrate the importance of integrating economic valuation of environmental impacts into sustainability assessments to identify trade-offs between environmental performance and socio-economic value. Quantifying environmental costs is essential for a comprehensive evaluation of soil systems, yet these costs are rarely included in agricultural and land management studies. The LCA-eCBA framework applied in this project addresses this gap by monetising externalities associated with different soil management practices

using a cradle-to-gate approach, which captures impacts at a global scale, often occurring far from the managed area.

An additional outcome is the fact that this methodology (LCA–eCBA framework) proved to be an effective double-checking tool, allowing cross-validation of results and the detection of potential inconsistencies. This added robustness check increases the reliability of the results and provides researchers, advisors and practitioners with a practical tool to identify environmental “hotspots” and to design soil management systems that are economically viable while enhancing soil functions, biodiversity and long-term ecosystem resilience.

Policy implications

The findings show that decisions based solely on private profitability can be misleading. For instance, in urban contexts, conventional cropland becomes economically inefficient once environmental costs are internalised through e-CBA. In contrast, sustainable management practices such as apple orchards, despite having higher environmental costs, achieve a clearly positive economic balance because the high market value of production compensates for both environmental and management costs.

Overall, these results confirm that sustainable soil management can reduce environmental pressures and, when combined with economic and social benefits, can justify public intervention. Such evidence supports the integration of environmental cost–benefit analysis into land-use planning, urban soil management strategies and agri-environmental schemes at both national and EU levels, contributing directly to the Soil Mission objectives on soil health, climate mitigation, biodiversity enhancement and the reduction of land degradation. Policy interventions may be based in alternative instruments: regulations, economic incentives (taxes, subsidies), so agents internalise social cost and benefits in their decision-making, etc.

Conclusion

The integration of e-CBA within InBestSoil demonstrates that monetising environmental impacts substantially changes the interpretation of soil management performance and reveals costs that remain invisible in conventional assessments. This report provides a robust and transferable framework to evaluate soil management practices on a common monetary basis, supporting evidence-based decisions across agricultural, urban, forest, and industrial contexts. The results establish a methodological foundation for subsequent InBestSoil activities, particularly for upscaling sustainability assessments, refining LLs/LHs comparisons, and supporting the design of soil health investment and policy instruments that ensure a resilient and climate-neutral European bioeconomy.

2. Objectives

Develop an integrated
LCA-eCBA
methodological
framework

Monetize
environmental
impacts (e-costs)

Standardize
results into a
single metric (€)

Assess social
sustainability and
trade-offs

Identify and
promote
sustainable
practices

Support
evidence-based
policy and
planning

3. Methodology

3.1. FRAMEWORK OF THE ENVIRONMENTAL COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is an analytical tool used to support decision-making by comparing the benefits and costs of different options in monetary terms. The benefits are defined as an increase in well-being, while costs represent decreases in well-being (OECD, 2018). By monetising and aggregating these factors, CBA helps to determine whether a proposed measure represents a net gain for society. It is typically applied when evaluating policy measures to ensure efficient resource allocation. The aim is to capture the full range of consequences of a project or measure for all members of society (Boardman et al., 2018).

There are two types of CBA: (i) ex-ante, to decide whether to allocate resources to a particular project or policy, and (ii) ex-post, to assess efficiency at different stages after the project is completed. Regardless of the typology, the steps to develop a CBA are clear, systematic and iterative, and evolve as the project matures to optimise the analysis. Thus, the methodology of a conventional CBA includes the steps shown in Figure 1. However, when market prices are used without adjustment, results may be distorted, as market prices rarely reflect environmental and social values (Hoogmartens et al., 2014).

Figure 1. Main steps in conducting a conventional cost-benefit analysis (CBA)

While financial (also termed private) cost-benefit analysis typically focuses on investment, operating, and management costs that are directly expressed in monetary terms, this analysis requires the inclusion of environmental and social externalities, which may occur off-site and over longer time horizons, and are often overlooked in conventional economic assessments (Babí Almenar et al., 2023; Finnveden et al. 2009). This highlights the importance of combining biophysical impact assessment with monetary valuation to support informed decision-making (Babí Almenar et al., 2023).

As a result, CBA has evolved beyond its traditional focus on purely financial returns, incorporating environmental considerations into its analytical framework, in response to the increasing demand for sustainable decision-making. This led to the development of **environmental cost-benefit analysis (hereafter e-CBA)**, in which environmental externalities are explicitly included in the assessment. E-CBA refers to the application of cost-benefit analysis to projects or that affect the natural environment as a direct or indirect consequence of their implementation (OECD, 2018). So, e-CBA is the approach used in this study as it ensures the integration of environmental criteria into the decision-making process (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic of the e-CBA. Source: OCDE 2018

Figure 3. Schematic framework illustrating the integration of LCA (environmental impacts) and e-CBA (environmental costs)

3.2. MONETARY VALUATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS

Economic assessment of environmental impact data derived from the LCA ensures that externalities are appropriately considered into decision-making. This approach goes beyond traditional LCA by assigning monetary values to environmental impacts, enabling a more comprehensive assessment of soil management interventions. The results support sustainable resource management and help policy makers to design more environmentally responsible land management strategies.

The analysis begins with the detailed LCA of each case study, which quantifies environmental impacts by tracking both inputs (e.g., energy, water) and outputs (e.g., emissions) (see deliverable D3.3 for details). In this report, we adopt the same **functional unit of 1 hectare of managed soil** as defined in the LCA ensuring consistency and compatibility between environmental and economic assessments. This approach enables a coherent comparison of impacts and performance across all soil management scenarios (see Figure 3)

Monetary valuation is the process of converting biophysical impact measurements into monetary units. It plays a key role in internalising externalities within economic systems, addressing market failures, and improving resource allocation (Pizzol et al., 2015). This is usually achieved by estimating the individual willingness to pay (WTP) to avoid negative impacts, or the willingness to accept (WTA) compensation for tolerating them. This helps to capture the social value of non-market goods and services, making environmental and social trade-offs more visible and actionable (Pearce and Barbier, 2000).

Several studies highlight the benefits of integrating monetary valuation into LCA, particularly during the weighting phase, where it allows aggregation of different impact categories into a single, interpretable metric (Ahlroth, 2014; Ahlroth et al., 2011; Finnveden et al., 2009; Amadei et al., 2021; Jeswani et al., 2010). Expressing environmental impacts in a common monetary unit facilitates direct comparison and supports evidence-based decision-making.

Approaches to monetary valuation

There are various methods for translating environmental impact categories from LCA into monetary values for inclusion in cost-benefit analyses (Amadei et al. 2021; Pizzol et al. 2015). Ideally, specific fieldwork using contingent valuation methods would be conducted to determine these values. However, due to time and budget constraints, this approach is not feasible within the InBestSoil project.

Instead, this report applies the **benefit transfer method**, which adjusts damage costs estimated in other contexts. This involves reviewing the economic literature and selecting studies that have analysed and monetised the environmental impacts identified in the LCA. The benefit transfer method uses monetary values of environmental goods from one context to estimate the value of similar goods in another, where their value is unknown (Navrud and Ready, 2007).

In the field of environmental economics, the method has been extensively tested, mainly in the US and Europe, with validations assessing the reliability of benefit transfer across locations and populations (Wilson and Hoehn, 2006; Boutwell and Westra, 2013).

For this study we have used the **Handbook of Environmental Prices developed by CE Delft (2024)**, which provides a practical and consistent approach. The environmental prices provided reflect the social cost of pollution, expressed in euros per kilogram of pollutant, representing the loss of economic welfare that occurs when an extra kilogram of a pollutant is released into the environment. The methodology includes midpoint characterization factors compatible with the ReCiPe 2016 framework, ensuring compatibility with the LCA-eCBA symbiosis. The **Handbook** provides prices at the European level (EU27) for the year 2021. This report will use the central case values recommended by the Handbook.

Using these environmental prices, we can assess the monetary value of the environmental impacts quantified by the LCA as part of the InBestSoil project. The values of these impact categories would be multiplied by the respective prices to estimate the external costs associated with these environmental impacts (Figure 3).

Data adjustments and aggregation

When applying the benefit transfer methodology, the original data should not be used directly. Instead, **adjustments are required to harmonise the information between studies**, ensuring well-defined value estimates for the target application areas. These adjustments must be consistent with the value definition, the valuation context, the theoretical basis of the value transfer, and the information available at the study site and policy site (Johnston et al. 2021).

For this case study, unit value transfer adjusted for spatial differences (EU prices) was applied. Damage cost estimates provided by the Handbook (EU27 average) were adapted to Spain, Croatia, Lithuania, Latvia, Italy, Netherlands, and Switzerland, assuming similar utility functions. As WTP for environmental quality increases with income, values were adjusted to reflect differences in income levels.

A major challenge in international benefit transfer is the variation in income levels and prices across countries. On the one hand, the national environmental prices should be correlated to the national income level (GDP per capita). On the other hand, there are important differences between countries in the value of an amount of money (e.g., 100 €), in terms of the quantity of goods and services it can buy (because of differences in prices). In that case, monetary comparisons must be done according to the purchasing power parity (PPP) of currencies. Within the European Union, GDP per capita in PPP terms (GDPpc PPP) differs between countries (Ready & Navrud, 2006). To account for these differences, GDPpc PPP was used as a proxy for income to translate the environmental prices provided by the Handbook (EU27 average) to the national context, following international recommendations for benefit transfer (Biausque, 2012).

The **spatial adjustment** was performed using an income elasticity of WTP (β) of 0.65, in line with the latest update of the Environmental Prices Handbook (2024). For EU countries, GDPpc PPP data for 2021 were obtained from [Eurostat](#) and expressed in euros. For Switzerland, which is not part of the euro zone, GDPpc PPP values were derived through a specific calculation procedure. PPP data originally expressed in Swiss francs were first converted into euros using the corresponding CHF–EUR conversion factor, ensuring consistency with the EU27 dataset.

Spatially adjusted WTP values were calculated applying the formula:

$$WTP_C = WTP_{EU27} (Y_C / Y_{EU27})^\beta$$

Where Y represents GDP per capita in PPP terms, $EU27$ refers to the reference study and C to the country of application, and β is the income elasticity. This procedure ensures a harmonised spatial adjustment across both euro and non-euro countries, allowing the inclusion of Switzerland without introducing distortions related to currency or purchasing power differences.

The InBestSoil project includes a heterogeneous collection of LH and LL, which makes cross-country comparisons useless. That means there is no benefit of using monetary valuations in PPP terms. Accordingly, national environmental prices were converted to Local Current Prices to make them comparable with data provided by the technoeconomic analysis from deliverable D3.2 - *Economic valuation of ecosystem services and disservices in LHs* (WP3, InBestSoil) (financial costs and benefits).

Additionally, a **temporal adjustment** is required since the environmental prices refer to the year 2021 (De Bruyn et al. 2023), and technoeconomic values and ecosystem services refer to 2024. Besides, we should account for the increase in income levels over time, due to the positive income elasticity of willingness to pay (WTP). Therefore, similarly to the territorial adjustment, an income-based adjustment is applied to update values over time. We estimated the WTP in 2024 based on the 2021 reference as follows:

$$WTP_{2024} = WTP_{2021} (Y_{2024} / Y_{2021})^\beta$$

Where Y_{2024} and Y_{2021} are GDP per capita in current prices at different points in time (source [Eurostat](#)), and β is the income elasticity of the demand for the environmental good. This temporal adjustment reflects changes in income levels over time as a result of changes in real income and prices.

As shown in Table 1, the adjusted environmental prices reflect the socio-economic diversity of the study sites. For instance, the valuation of Global Warming impacts ranges from 0.09 €/kg CO₂-eq in Croatia and Latvia to 0.32€/kg CO₂-eq in Switzerland. These differences are strictly correlated with the differences in purchasing power and economic growth (GDP current prices) between 2021 and 2024, ensuring that environmental externalities are economically assessed according to the local economic context of each InBestSoil case study

Finally, it should be noted that the **environmental costs** calculated through the LCA-e-CBA framework **cover the entire value chain (cradle-to-gate approach)**. Consequently, a substantial share of the impacts may occur outside the physical boundaries of the managed or restored areas. This includes upstream impacts, such as those from the production of external inputs (e.g. fertilizers or chemical products). Including these stages allows for a more complete estimation of the net environmental costs of the management practices implemented.

Table 1. Summary of the environmental prices (€ per unit of impact) for the EU27 (2021) and selected European countries (2024), derived using spatial and temporal adjustments

Impact categories	Units	Central value UE-27 (*)	Spain	Croatia	Italy	Latvia	Lithuania	Netherlands	Switzerland
Global warming (GWP)	€/kg CO ₂ eq	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.14	0.09	0.10	0.21	0.32
Stratospheric ozone depletion (ODP)	€/kg CFC-11-eq	29.1	27.9	19.1	31.1	19.7	22.5	46.2	72.5
Ionizing radiation (IR)	€/kBq Co-60-eq	0.00422	0.00405	0.00277	0.00452	0.00286	0.00326	0.00669	0.01052
Ozone formation, Human health (OF-HH)	€/kg NO _x -eq	1.86	1.79	1.22	1.99	1.26	1.44	2.95	4.63
Fine particulate matter formation (PMF)	€/kg PM _{2.5} -eq	84.7	81.3	55.7	90.6	57.3	65.5	134.4	211.0
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems (OF-TE)	€/kg NO _x -eq	0.416	0.399	0.273	0.445	0.281	0.322	0.660	1.037
Terrestrial acidification (TA)	€/kg SO ₂ -eq	5.28	5.07	3.47	5.65	3.57	4.08	8.38	13.16
Freshwater eutrophication (FE)	€/kg P-eq	3.74	3.59	2.46	4.00	2.53	2.89	5.93	9.32
Marine eutrophication (ME)	€/kg N-eq	14.25	13.68	9.37	15.25	9.64	11.02	22.61	35.51
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (TET)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.00064	0.00061	0.00042	0.00068	0.00043	0.00049	0.00102	0.00159
Freshwater ecotoxicity (FET)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.0209	0.0201	0.0137	0.0224	0.0141	0.0162	0.0332	0.0521
Marine ecotoxicity (MET)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.0032	0.0031	0.0021	0.0034	0.0022	0.0025	0.0051	0.0080
Human carcinogenic toxicity (HCT)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	3.99	3.83	2.62	4.27	2.70	3.08	6.33	9.94
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT)	€/kg 1,4-DCB-eq	0.071	0.068	0.047	0.076	0.048	0.055	0.113	0.177

(*) Values taken from the Handbook of Environmental Prices 2024 - ReCiPe 2016 midpoints, in €2021 per unit for EU27

3.3. INTEGRATION OF MANAGEMENT COSTS AND PRODUCTION BENEFITS IN THE E-CBA FRAMEWORK

After quantifying environmental costs through monetisation of environmental impacts, financial data were integrated to complete the e-CBA framework (see Figure 4). For each Living Lab (LL) and Lighthouse (LH), investment costs, operation and maintenance (O&M) costs, and production revenues were combined with environmental externalities to estimate the overall socioeconomic balance.

The economic dataset from the deliverable D3.2 provides a harmonised market-based valuation of soil uses across agricultural, forestry, and urban systems. This information is based on technical data provided by LL/LH experts and case study leaders (e.g., inputs, labour, yields, and management characteristics), complemented by statistical sources when needed. This ensures methodological consistency across case studies.

In addition to market values (costs and revenues), D3.2 also provides non-market monetary estimates of ecosystem services. In this framework, social value is captured through the monetisation of environmental externalities (environmental costs and ecosystem services). D3.2 provides monetary estimates of ecosystem services according to spatial adjustment (GDP per capita in PPP terms). As explained previously, the full integration of all costs and benefits required the conversion of those values in PPP to Local Current Prices, to make them comparable with data provided by the technoeconomic analysis (financial costs and benefits). To ensure consistency, all values are expressed in €/ha per year. That means investment cost should be annualised (e.g., implementation of Technosols in LH2 and LH3, or tree planting in LH6). A lifetime of 68 years was assumed for Technosols and 20 years for forest systems, in line with D3.2.

Figure 4. Integrated e-CBA framework for Social Margin Calculations

This harmonised treatment allows direct comparison between O&M costs, annualised investments, production revenues, and environmental externalities, enabling the estimation of net social balances for each soil management system (Figure 4).

4. Results

This section presents the consolidated e-CBA results derived from the analysis of 9 case studies, including 7 Lighthouses (LH) and 2 Living Labs (LL), covering a diverse range of European soil uses. These case studies cover agriculture, forestry, urban, and industrial land uses across four biogeographical regions in Europe: Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, and Mediterranean (Figure 5).

To ensure methodological consistency with the LCA, direct field emission data (measured on-site for gases like CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O) were excluded from the total environmental cost calculations. This decision was based on the fact that these specific field measurements are highly sensitive to short-term climatic and seasonal conditions, which could introduce significant uncertainty and bias into long-term assessments.

Consequently, the **analysis focuses strictly on management-related impacts**, such as machinery operations, transport, and the production of inputs, ensuring a reliable, transparent, and robust evaluation of the environmental costs directly associated with soil management practices.

Figure 5. Overview of the nine case studies within the InBestSoil project (LH 1-7 and LL 8-9)

4.1. INDUSTRIAL SOILS

LH2 – MEDITERRANEAN INDUSTRIAL SOIL (CARTAGENA, SPAIN): RESTORATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL BY MINING ACTIVITIES USING ARTIFICIAL SOILS (TECHNOSOLS)

This LH is focused on the restoration of contaminated soil, severely degraded by intense mining activities which resulted in heavy metal contamination, acidification, sulfation and salinization, leading to an almost complete loss of vegetation cover (Figure 6).

Figure 6. LH2 area: before (left) and after (right) restoration

The intervention applied combines the application of artificial soils (Technosols) composed of organic (slurry and manure) and inorganic materials (mine tailings and marble waste), together with an assisted phytostabilization phase through the establishment of metal-tolerant plant species. This integrated approach was designed to immobilize contaminants, improve soil health and restore key regulating ecosystem functions.

The **total environmental cost** of the intervention was estimated as **178 €/ha**. The application of Technosols was identified as the main contributor phase, accounting 69 €/ha (39% of the total e-cost), primarily due to fuel consumption for machinery operation and material transport (Figure 7). The crop establishment phase accounted for 52 €/ha, largely driven by seedling production, which represented almost the entire environmental burden of this activity.

Figure 7. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the remediation process implemented in the LH2

Figure 8. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH2

The environmental costs were concentrated in three impact categories: fine particulate matter formation (PMF: 43.4%), global warming potential (GWP: 22.9%) and human toxicity (HCT+HNCT: 26%), reflecting the **relevance of emissions related to material handling, soil amendments and establishment** activities in a heavily degraded mining context (Figure 8).

The results should be interpreted considering that no active management takes place under the non-intervention scenario. Therefore, this analysis captures the added environmental pressures generated by the restoration activities themselves.

From **a financial perspective**, adding environmental costs to the high initial investment (101,746 €/ha) results in a **clearly negative short-term balance**, as no direct market revenues are generated. However, the intervention in LH2 should be considered a one-time capital investment needed to remediate a severely degraded site. Both **investment and environmental costs occur at the beginning of the project** and no recurrent maintenance costs are assumed during the expected lifetime of the Technosols.

Therefore, the calculated environmental costs (178 €/ha) must be annualised over a 68-year period in the same way as the first investment (in line with D3.2 calculations). This resulted in an equivalent **environmental cost of 2.62 €/ha per year**, enabling a direct comparison with the annual flows of ecosystem services and ensuring methodological consistency within the e-CBA framework (Table 2). Overall, the annual environmental burden resulting is insignificant in relation to the magnitude of the restoration effort, being **only 0.17% of the total costs**.

However, the financial result does not represent the overall social value of the intervention. According to the non-market values, presented in deliverable D3.2, **the restoration generates substantial non-market benefits through improved ecosystem services**, such as soil stabilization, reduced contaminant mobility and enhanced regulating functions. The increase in ecosystem service value has been estimated at approximately 24,243 €/ha per year compared to the non-intervention baseline. Over the long term, these benefits largely offset the initial restoration investment, **resulting in a strongly positive social outcome** (+22,744 €/ha year) (Table 1).

Table 2. e-CBA performance of LH2 Forest (€/ha per year)

LH2		BS (No action)	MP (Restoration)	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenues	0.00	0.00	0.00
	I+O&M costs	0.00	1,496.27	1,496.27
Non-market	Environmental costs	0.00	2.62	2.62
	Ecosystem services	35,869.73	60,112.74	24,243.02
Social Margin		35,869.73	58,613.85	22,744.13

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. Social margin = market margin + non-market margin

LH3 – ATLANTIC INDUSTRIAL SOIL (TOURO, SPAIN) – RESTORATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL BY COPPER MINING ACTIVITIES USING TECHNOSOLS

This case study focuses on soil restoration in an area highly affected by copper mining. The study area presented extreme degradation, including severe soil and water pollution, hyperacidification, hyperoxidation, hypersulfation, hyperaluminization and important levels of metallic contamination, among others. The remediation strategy applied consist of producing and applying artificial soils (Technosols) specifically designed to neutralize acidity, immobilize heavy metals, and improve soil structure and fertility (Figure 9).

Figure 9. LH3 area of restoration, before and after the soil intervention

In LH3, Technosols were produced using industrial and organic by-products, including ashes from combustion of woody debris biomass, (produced by the pulp mill from the ENCE factory), sewage sludge, residual aluminium gels (from aluminium extrusion industries), mussel shell waste, crushed biomass and filler from crushing amphibolite and schist to obtain road aggregates (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Closeup of the Technosols applied in the LH3 intervention

The total environmental cost of the intervention reached **5,110 €/ha**. These impacts are entirely linked to the remediation process including Technosols production, transport, and field application.

From a process perspective, **Technosols production accounts for approximately 60%** of total environmental costs (3,100 €/ha), confirming that upstream activities related to material preparation and mixing are the main environmental hotspots. During the application phase, truck loading is the most impactful activity (898 €/ha), followed by transport to the site (667 €/ha) and soil spreading (445 €/ha) (Figure 11). These findings highlight the importance of logistics management in large-scale soil remediation projects.

Figure 11. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the remediation process implemented in the LH3

Figure 12. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH3

The environmental impact is concentrated in three impact categories: **human non-carcinogenic toxicity** (HNCT, 39.6%), **fine particulate matter formation** (PMF, 30.4%) and **global warming potential** (GWP, 21.5%), reflecting the relevance of emissions linked to material handling, machinery use and transport of large volumes of Technosols constituents (Figure 12).

These results must be interpreted considering the extremely degraded baseline conditions. Under the no-action scenario, no active management takes place. Therefore, the assessment reflects only the added environmental pressures generated by the restoration works.

When the environmental costs are internalised into the **economic assessment**, the restoration have shown a **clearly negative balance**, linked to high investment costs (129,790 €/ha) and no market direct revenues generated. This measure should be understood as a one-time capital intervention aimed at restoring a severely degraded mining site. Both the **investment and the associated environmental impacts occur at the beginning of the project** and no recurrent maintenance costs are expected over the lifetime of Technosols.

So, the total environmental impacts quantified at 5,110 €/ha must be annualised over the same 68-year time horizon applied to the investment costs (consistent with the approach

in D3.2). This results in an **annual environmental cost of 75.16 €/ha per year**. Applying this temporal harmonization allows environmental costs, annualised investment costs and ecosystem service to be assessed on a comparable basis, thereby ensuring internal consistency within the e-CBA framework (Table 3).

Table 3. e-CBA performance of LH3

LH3		BS (No action)	MP (Restoration)	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenue	0.00	0.00	0.00
	Cost	0.00	1,908.68	1,908.68
Non-market	Environmental costs	0.00	75.16	75.16
	Ecosystem services	192,656.75	226,882.57	34,225.82
Social Margin		192,656.75	224,898.73	32,241.98

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. Social margin = market margin + non-market margin

Overall, the annual environmental burden resulting from this is low in relation to the size of the restoration effort, being **only 4% of the total costs**.

However, this financial result does not represent the overall social value of the intervention. According to the non-market valuation presented in deliverable D3.2, this restoration provides key benefits such as contaminant immobilisation, acid neutralisation, recovery of soil functions, reduced risks to water bodies, carbon sequestration and landscape restoration. The increase in ecosystem service value has been estimated at approximately 34,226 €/ha per year compared to the non-intervention baseline. Over the long term, these benefits largely offset the annualised costs, **resulting in a strongly positive social outcome** (+32,242 €/ha year) (Table 3).

Overall, these results illustrate that even capital-intensive remediation projects remain socially justified once environmental externalities and ecosystem service gains are jointly considered.

4.2. URBAN SOILS

LH4 –CONTINENTAL URBAN SOIL (ZAGREB, CROATIA) – CARBON SEQUESTRATION AND FLOOD MITIGATION CAPACITY OF AGRICULTURAL AND FOREST USES IN URBAN SOILS

The LH4 focuses on urban soils in the continental region of Zagreb (Croatia), which are affected by long-term overexploitation and unsustainable land management. The reference soil is characterised by low organic carbon content, soil compaction, structural degradation, reduced biodiversity, land abandonment and an increased risk of flooding. These conditions limit the capacity of urban soil to provide key ecosystem services, particularly water regulation and carbon sequestration. For that, the restoration efforts focus on the **application of different sustainable management practices including**

mulching, minimal soil disturbance, permanent grass cover and optimised fertilization, which significantly improve soil health.

The study compares two different areas where sustainable soil management practices have been implemented (grassland and apple orchard), together with a nearby control area under annual cropland management (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Overview of LH4 land uses (from left to right): annual cropland, apple orchard, and grassland

Figure 14. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the management practices implemented in the LH4

Environmental costs vary substantially across land uses, reflecting differences in management intensity and input requirements (Figure 14). The lowest environmental costs are associated with grasslands, with a total of 31 €/ha. This system is characterised by low-intensity practices, mainly mulching activities and permanent vegetation cover, with no soil disturbance and no fertilization.

In contrast, the **apple orchard presents the highest reaching 438 €/ha. Fertilization is the dominant contributor** to environmental burden, accounting for more than 50% of total environmental costs (230 €/ha). Despite the adoption of sustainable practices such as mulching and permanent grass cover, the higher input intensity needed to sustain fruit production leads to increased emissions, particularly related to climate change, human toxicity and ecotoxicity-related impact categories. This result highlights that input-intensive operations remain a key environmental hotspot, even under improved management strategies.

The conventional **annual cropland has shown relatively high environmental costs (344 €/ha)**, driven mainly by **soil preparation and harvesting activities**. These two stages together account for more than 65% of total environmental costs, reflecting high diesel consumption and intensive machinery use. This combined with intensive mineral fertilisation, further contributes to the environmental burden of this system.

Overall, grassland management reduces environmental costs by 91% compared to conventional annual cropland, while the apple orchard increases environmental costs by approximately 27% compared to the baseline. These results clearly demonstrate the strong influence of land use and management intensity on environmental performance.

Differences across systems are also observed in the variations through impact categories contributions (Figure 15). **Grassland management shows a strong reduction in human toxicity** (cancer effects) linked to the absence of fertilizers and pesticides. In addition, **marine eutrophication (ME) plays a significant role in conventional cropland** but is negligible in the sustainable alternatives, with reductions of 78% for the apple orchard and 98% for grasslands. This pattern is directly linked to the reduced nutrient losses associated with permanent vegetation cover and improved soil structure.

These results confirm that sustainable soil management practices in urban areas can substantially reduce environmentally relevant pressures, particularly those related to nutrient losses and toxic emissions.

Figure 15. Seven main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH4

The integration of environmental externalities (environmental costs and ecosystem services) into economic assessment is illustrated in Table 4 and Figure 16

The **annual cropland (baseline)** system, characterised by conventional tillage, intensive mineral fertilisation and the absence of cover crops or mulching, shows high environmental costs (344 €/ha) and production costs (1,353 €/ha), while revenues from winter wheat production are relatively low (857 €/ha). This results in an almost neutral or slightly negative economic balance even before environmental externalities are considered. When environmental costs are included, the system becomes **clearly inefficient from both an environmental and economic perspective (-840 €/ha)**. Environmental costs represent 20% of total costs, underlining the importance of including externalities in economic evaluations.

The **apple orchard** under sustainable management presents the highest environmental costs (438 €/ha), but it also generates substantially higher economic benefits (11,130 €/ha), despite relatively high production costs (6,416 €/ha). As a result, the integrated analysis indicates a strongly positive economic balance (+4,276 €/ha), suggesting that the economic value of apple production is sufficient to compensate for the associated environmental costs. In this system, environmental costs represented only the 9% of total costs, suggesting that high-value production can absorb environmental externalities when sustainable practices are applied.

For **grasslands**, the absence of direct market costs prevents calculations.

Table 4. e-CBA performance of LH4 Forest (€/ha per year)

LH4		Annual cropland (BS)	Apple orchard	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenues	857.00	11,130.00	10,273.00
	Management costs	1,353.00	6,416.00	-5,063.00
Non-market	Environmental costs	343.93	437.89	-93.96
	Ecosystem services	15,292.74	14,322.14	-970.59
Social Margin		14,452.81	18,598.25	4,145.45

Overall, both systems are socio-economically efficient once ecosystem services are accounted for (Figure 16). However, the apple orchard achieves a higher net social gain due to the combination of substantial market revenues and sustained provision of ecosystem services (Table 4), demonstrating that soil-health-oriented management can align private profitability with broader societal benefits.

Figure 16. Integrated socio-economic balance (€/ha per year) of the annual cropland and the sustainably managed apple orchard (LH4)

LH5 – BOREAL URBAN SOIL (VILNIUS, LITHUANIA) – IMPACT OF URBAN AGRICULTURE ON SOIL HEALTH

This LH focuses on soil threats of boreal urban soils like flood risk, soil erosion, compaction, pollution, reduced biodiversity and low organic content. The intervention consists in the implementation of **sustainable urban gardening**, including a variety of crops (cucumber, tomato, onion, pumpkin and strawberries), and practices such as composting, mulching, no tillage and the avoidance of agrochemicals (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Photos of the LH5 intervention: aerial view of the site and detailed view of the urban garden analysed

The **environmental costs** associated with urban gardening practices implemented in LH5 amount to a total of **6 €/ha** (Figure 18). Analysing the contribution per activity, **land management practices** (including composting or mulching) are **the main driver of environmental costs**, accounting for 72% of the total, together with fertilisation contributing 22% while irrigation has a negligible contribution, reflecting the low intensity or limited use of water inputs in the system.

Figure 18. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the urban gardening practices implemented in LH5

In terms of **impact categories**, Human toxicity (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) is the dominant category, accounting for 47% of total costs. This is followed by global warming potential (GWP) and fine particulate matter formation (PMF), each contributing 23%, while all remaining categories individually contribute 3% or less, showing a limited relevance in the overall impact profile (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Main impact categories contributing to the total environmental costs in LH5

When environmental costs are incorporated into the economic assessment, the LH5 intervention shows a clear **contrast between environmental burden and management effort** (Table 5). While environmental costs are minimal (6 €/ha), production costs are relatively high (198 €/ha), reflecting the labour-intensive nature of urban gardening and soil improvement practices such as composting, mulching and diversified cropping.

Market revenues from vegetable production (e.g. cucumber, tomato, onion) amount to 335 €/ha, resulting in a modest but positive private margin. If only direct costs and revenues are considered, the practice can be characterised by **low environmental impact and limited but positive economic performance**.

However, the overall contribution of LH5 extends beyond direct revenues. Total ecosystem services valuation was estimated at 32,144 €/ha per year, highlighting substantial social and environmental benefits. This value reflects the comprehensive social valuation of the urban garden, and therefore it is specific to the land-use option assessed. Nevertheless, this assessment does not include the performance under alternative urban green space designs or management schemes. For instance, a full CBA should consider alternative uses like a grass garden (i.e., it will provide an extra 4,900 €/ha of ES, will provide zero revenues, and different management and environmental cost). Unfortunately, the data provided by this case study is limited and prevents us from doing all these calculations.

Table 5. e-CBA performance of LH5 (€/ha/year)

LH5 – Urban Garden		€/ha per year
Market	Revenues	335
	Management costs	198
Non-market	Environmental costs	6
	Ecosystem services	32,144.33
Social Margin		32,274.68

Consequently, when **externalities are integrated** into the e-CBA framework, the social margin reaches 32,275 €/ha per year, clearly showing a **strongly positive social value**. Environmental costs are only around 3% of total private costs, reinforcing that LH5 constitutes a low-impact urban land-use option with moderate economic performance but substantial socio-environmental value, contributing primarily to local food provision and community benefits.

4.3. AGRICULTURAL SOILS

LH7 – ATLANTIC AGRICULTURAL SOIL (BETUWE, NETHERLAND) – REGENERATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT FOR IMPROVED NUTRIENT CYCLES AND SOIL HEALTH

The LH7 focuses on an agricultural soil where sustainable methods are applied to improve soil health. These biodynamic and regenerative practices, consist of broad crop rotations, use of green manure, reduced tillage, and the use of nitrogen-fixing crops (Figure 20). This intervention was compared against a conventional system with the aim of evaluating and quantifying the impact that these practices have on soil health enhancement.

Management in the **biodynamic and regenerative system** relies on organic seeds, green manures, reduced tillage and no use of chemical inputs. In contrast, the **conventional system** uses conventional seeds, mineral fertilizers, herbicides and fungicides and reliance on external inputs for pest control and soil fertility.

Figure 20. Photos of the biodynamic and regenerative systems under study

The monetisation of environmental impacts reveals **substantial differences between conventional and organic** crop management systems. Total environmental costs **decreased by 33% when shifting from conventional to organic management**, falling from 696 €/ha to 467 €/ha (Figure 21), highlighting the overall environmental advantage of biodynamic and regenerative practices.

The results also confirmed a clear shift in the sources of environmental pressure. In the **conventional system, agricultural machinery is the main contributor** to environmental costs (524€/ha), followed by fertilisation and pest management. In contrast, under organic management machinery-related costs decrease by 43% and fertilization costs by 77%. Environmental costs linked to synthetic pesticides are fully eliminated.

Conversely, sowing with organic seeds shows a higher environmental cost compared to conventional seeds, reflecting more resource-intensive seed production processes, but this increase is widely compensated by reductions in all other management stages.

Figure 21. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the two farming systems under study in LH7

Figure 22. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the two farming systems in LH7

About impact categories, organic management reduces costs in almost all categories. The most significant reduction is observed for **global warming potential (-57%)**, ionising radiation (-88%), human carcinogenic toxicity (-79%), freshwater eutrophication (-78%), and terrestrial ecotoxicity (-78%) (Figure 22). These reductions are mainly linked to the absence of synthetic fertilisers and pesticides and to the lower fuel consumption. Only marine eutrophication increases, rising from 10 to 20 €/ha, though its contribution to total costs is still limited.

When environmental costs are internalised in the economic analysis, the results clearly favour the organic system. As shown in the Table 6, while **conventional farming supports a small positive private margin (107 €/ha)**, when environmental costs are included, the system becomes negative (-588.72 €/ha), showing that the environmental damage exceeds the economic profit.

In contrast, the **organic system generates a positive balance**, supported by lower management costs (1,681 €/ha), higher revenues (3,210 €/ha), and reduced environmental costs. This shows that regenerative and biodynamic practices not only reduce environmental externalities but also improve overall socio-economic efficiency (Figure 23).

In both systems studied, **environmental costs are a substantial share of production costs: about 20%**. This shows that these impacts are a significant part of the full cost of farming. Ignoring these often-overlooked costs can give a wrong picture of economic performance of agricultural systems and lead to poor management decisions. Including them in the e-CBA framework is essential for clear, complete, and useful sustainability assessments.

Figure 23. Revenues, management costs (investment + O&M) and environmental costs for conventional and organic farming in LH7

By incorporating the valuation of ecosystem services (ES), a broader sustainability perspective is provided, internalising both negative externalities (environmental costs) and positive externalities (ecosystem services) (Table 6). Organic management increases the value of economic services by 19% compared to conventional farming. Consequently, the **social margin under organic management reaches 24% higher than the conventional**

system (an absolute increase of +7,457 €/ha per year). These results prove that organic management is not only a viable economic alternative but also a necessary strategy for supporting social and environmental sustainability in Atlantic agricultural systems.

Table 6. e-CBA performance of LH7 (€/ha peryear)

LH7		Conventional (BS)	Organic	Δ €/ha per year
Market	Revenues	2,413.00	3,210.00	797.00
	Costs	2,306.00	1,681.00	-625.00
Non-market	Environmental costs	695.72	467.10	-228.62
	Ecosystem services	31,155.38	36,961.53	5,806.15
Social Margin		30,566.66	38,023.43	7,456.77

The results of LH7 show that **organic and regenerative management reduces environmental pressures, improves economic performance, and increases social value**, reinforcing its relevance as a sustainable pathway for improving soil health and nutrient cycling in Atlantic agricultural systems.

LL1 – MEDITERRANEAN AGRICULTURAL SOIL (SARDINIA, ITALY) – ALTERNATIVE CROP MANAGEMENT AS POTENTIAL CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION

The intensive agricultural practices and increase challenge environmental conditions driven by climate change are deteriorating soil fertility and health in the Mediterranean region. This degradation diminishing agricultural profitability and leading to the abandonment of cultivated land.

Intervention in LL1 was focus on the application of conservation agriculture incorporating a set of practices focused on conserving water and soil through reduced soil disturbance (reduced tillage and sod seeding), permanent soil cover, and crop rotations (see Figure 24).

Figure 24. Photographs from LL1 show the conventional tillage and sod seeding management practices

Environmental costs associated to the practices implemented in LL1 highlights the considerable influence of soil management on overall environmental performance (Figure 25). Under **conventional tillage**, **total environmental costs amount to 281 €/ha**. Sowing represents the largest contribution (approximately 50% of total costs), mainly due to impacts associated with seed production and machinery use, including fuel consumption. Soil preparation and crop maintenance also account for significant shares of the overall environmental burden (76 and 63 €/ha, respectively), while harvesting has a marginal contribution (4 €/ha).

About the two sustainable practices analysed, **reduced tillage** significantly lowers environmental costs, with a **24% reduction compared to conventional tillage** (total e-costs 213 €/ha). This improvement is mainly explained by the substantial decrease in impacts associated with soil preparation (8 €/ha). On the other hand, **sod seeding achieves the lowest environmental burden**, with total costs of 205 €/ha (**27% reduction** compared to the conventional baseline). In this system, soil preparation is eliminated, which explains the added reduction observed relative to reduced tillage (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the remediation process implemented in the LL1

Figure 26. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LL1

Environmental impacts are mainly driven by two categories across the three management systems: **global warming potential (GWP)** and **particulate matter formation (PMF)**.

Together, they account for **around 65–70% of total environmental costs** in all scenarios (Figure 26). In conventional tillage, GWP represents 97 €/ha and PMF 96 €/ha. A similar pattern is observed in reduced tillage and sod seeding, although absolute values decrease due to lower overall fuel consumption and reduced soil disturbance. Differences between management practices are mainly explained by variations in toxicity-related and air-emission categories. Thus, **conventional tillage shows higher contributions from human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HNCT, 10%) and ozone formation** for human health (OF-HH, 2%), which are linked to more intensive machinery use and associated fuel combustion.

An integrated economic balance for LL1 could not be performed due to inconsistencies between the LCA inventory and the economic datasets provided in D3.2.

LL2 – CONTINENTAL AGRICULTURAL SOIL (BASELLAND, SWITZERLAND) – CLIMATE MITIGATION THROUGH SOIL ORGANIC MATTER ACCUMULATION AND BUILT-UP

This Living Lab focuses on agricultural soils facing multiple sustainability challenges, including soil organic matter (SOM) depletion, loss of soil biodiversity, erosion risk, and diffuse pollution of soil and water driven by intensive farming practices. These pressures reduce long-term soil fertility and resilience, limiting the capacity of agricultural systems to contribute to climate mitigation and sustainable food production.

Two experimental sites were analysed: a **biodynamic farming system**, characterised by diversified crop rotations and reduced chemical inputs, and a **conventional farming system**, based on intensive arable production (Figure 27). Several plots within each system represent different management goals, ranging from food and feed production to ecosystem service-oriented practices, such as nectar production for pollinators and SOM accumulation without harvesting (Table 7).

Figure 27. Overview of the two different experimental sites in LL2, showing the biodynamic system (left) and the conventional system (right)

Table 7. Description of the different management strategies implemented in LL2

Agricultural system	Plots	Crops	Management practices
Biodynamic	LL2_1-3	Faba bean+triticale	crop production with mulching, shallow tillage, organic fertilization harvest
	LL2_4-6	Lentils + oats	crop production with mulching, shallow tillage organic fertilization mechanical weed control harvest
	LL2_7-9	Flowers	not harvested support pollinators by producing nectar
	LL2_13-15	Barley	not harvested accumulate SOM to enhance long term soil health and fertility
Conventional	LL2_16-18	Barley	arable plot
	LL2_19-21	Fodder (hay and silage)	intensive production
	LL2_22-24	Wheat	arable plots

Environmental costs in the **biodynamic system** show high variability across management practices, ranging from approximately **652 to 1,578 €/ha** (Figure 28).

Higher environmental costs within the biodynamic system are associated with **faba bean** (1578 €/ha) and **mountain lentils** crops (965 €/ha). In both cases, fertilisation is the dominant contributor, accounting for around 55–60% of total environmental burden. This result highlights the **environmental relevance of organic and processed fertilisers**, particularly in relation to human toxicity impact categories (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic) (Figure 29). Soil preparation and sowing together represent approximately 20–30% of total costs, reflecting machinery use and fuel consumption. Harvesting contributes relatively little to total environmental costs (around 13% for faba bean plots and 5% for lentil plots), indicating that upstream input production and soil management are more relevant environmental hotspots (Figure 28).

Nectar production practice, designed to support pollinators and biodiversity without harvesting, present unexpectedly high environmental costs (1,270 €/ha) despite of the simplicity of this management approach. These costs are mainly driven by tillage (731 €/ha) and sowing activities (539 €/ha). The results suggest that the environmental burden is linked to intensive machinery use which is reflected in high contributions from global warming potential (GWP) and fine particulate matter formation (PMF) (Figure 29).

SOM accumulation practice shows the lowest environmental costs within the biodynamic farming system (652 €/ha). In this case, sowing operations dominate the impacts, accounting for nearly 80% of total costs, likely due to the use of complex seed mixtures application and repeated operations.

Figure 28. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the biodynamic systems analysed in the LL2

Figure 29. Contribution of the main impact categories to the total environmental costs in the different management practices under biodynamic farming systems

Environmental costs in the **conventional system** range from **116 to 1,440 €/ha**, showing strong contrasts between different crop types and management intensities (Figure 30).

Fodder production shows the lowest environmental costs (116 €/ha) among conventional practices. This low impact is explained by the absence of soil tillage, mineral fertilisation, and pesticide use, with environmental burdens mainly linked to slurry application and mowing.

Conventional **barley** production shows moderate environmental costs (310 €/ha), with soil preparation, sowing, and fertilisation contributing in relatively similar proportions. This reflects a lower-intervention annual cropping system compared to wheat.

In contrast, **wheat** cultivation presents the highest environmental costs (1,440 €/ha) among conventional practices. Nearly 50% of total costs are associated with soil preparation, driven by intensive tillage operations such as mulching and deep ploughing. This is clearly reflected in higher contributions from GWP and PMF, linked to diesel

consumption and machinery use (Figure 31). Fertilisation further increases environmental burdens, particularly in eutrophication-related categories.

Figure 30. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the conventional systems analysed in the LL2

Figure 31. Contribution of the main impact categories to the total environmental costs in the different management practices under conventional farming systems

When **external costs are incorporated into the economic assessment**, the results prove significant variability across different management practices. In most cases, internalising environmental costs significantly worsens the economic balance with only 2 scenarios maintaining a positive balance, confirming that private profitability alone does not reflect real sustainability performance (Table 8).

Table 8. Cost-Benefit Analysis (e-CBA) results for the evaluated scenarios

LL2	Biodynamic				Conventional		
	Faba bean	Lentils	Nectar production	SOM	Barley	Fodder	Wheat
Management costs	7,258	8,118	400	9,141	966	301	2,233
Revenues	4,869	9,823	0	0	277	544	471
Environmental costs	1,578	1,045	1,270	652	310	117	1,440
Social margin (*) without ES	-3,967	660	-1,670	-9,793	-999	126	-3,202
% e-costs	18%	11%	76%	7%	24%	28%	39%

All values in €/ha per year

(*) **Social margin** values include only environmental costs (negative externalities). Non-market ecosystem services (ES; positive externalities) are not accounted for due to data limitations.

Figure 32. Annual economic and environmental performance (€/ha per year) of biodynamic and conventional agricultural practices in LL2

The **lentils system** under biodynamic management **shows the strongest overall performance**. This is the only biodynamic productive crop with a positive margin after internalising environmental costs (660 €/ha), combining high private profitability with the lowest relative environmental pressure (11% of total costs).

Conversely, **conventional wheat performs worst among productive systems**, with a negative private margin (-1,762 €/ha), which increases to -3,202 €/ha when environmental costs are included. These costs are 39% of total costs, highlighting the important environmental burden of conventional wheat crops relative to the economic value generated.

It is interesting to highlight the **SOM accumulation scenario as a soil restoration strategy rather than a productive system**. Although income is zero and the private margin is negative (-9,141 €/ha), environmental costs being only 7% of total costs. This shows

minimal environmental pressure compared to financial effort, suggesting that SOM-focused practices could be environmentally efficient despite requiring short-term economic investment.

Nectar production stands out for its **high environmental impact** with environmental costs accounting for 76% of the total. This suggests that the intervention has a significant operational footprint due to the substantial use of machinery and other resources, which could be optimised. It should be noted that the current assessment does not include positive externalities, such as improved biodiversity and associated ecosystem services (e.g., pollination and pest control, delivering nectar for bees). Including these benefits could substantially alter the results, potentially lower the environmental burden, and highlight the broader ecological value of this practice.

Fodder is the only conventional crop that supports a positive margin once environmental costs are internalising (126 €/ha). The environmental costs represent 28% of total costs, and its relative environmental load is still higher than that of conventional barley or SOM accumulation, showing that economic viability is achieved at a relatively high environmental cost.

Overall, the LL2 management practices show that some biodynamic practices clearly outperform conventional system (e.g. lentils), while others involve strongly negative balances (e.g. SOM accumulation) (Figure 32). These results suggest that sustainability is driven more by crop design and specific management practices than by the production system alone.

It is important to note that the estimated social margins for LL2 are likely conservative, as specific non-market values of ecosystem service are not available for each of these scenarios. Therefore, the current assessment only captures the internalisation of negative externalities (environmental costs). As a result, the total social value is only partially reflected, excluding relevant benefits in the case of biodynamic practices such as carbon sequestration, cultural heritage functions, or biodiversity support.

4.4. FORESTRY SOILS

LH1 – MEDITERRANEAN FORESTRY SOIL (EXTREMADURA, SPAIN) – RESTORATION OF SOIL BY ROTATIONAL GRAZING MANAGING IN WOODY PASTURES

Mediterranean forestry soil is characterised by low biodiversity, erosion risk, overgrazing, reduced soil organic matter and overall low soil quality. To address these soil threats, a sustainable management strategy based on regenerative rotational grazing has been implemented (Figure 33). This practice avoids tillage and sowing, applies short periods of high grazing intensity followed by sufficient resting time and uses autochthonous cattle and sheep breeds.

The goal of this practice is to improve soil structure, enhance vegetation cover, increase soil organic matter, and promote biodiversity, while maintaining productive land use through meat production.

Figure 33. Photos of the Mediterranean forestry soil abandoned (left) and under rotational grazing practices (right)

Environmental costs associated to the management practice implemented in LH1 amount to **354 €/ha**, reflecting that the environmental burden is mainly driven by livestock-related activities (livestock emissions: 89 €/ha, and feeding: 238 €/ha) accounting for more than 99% of the total environmental costs (Figure 34). This highlighted that the animal production processes in the central role in the overall environmental performance of this practice applied in the Mediterranean soil.

Among impact categories, **global warming is the dominant contributor, representing 33 % of total environmental costs (104 €/ha)**, followed by human non-carcinogenic toxicity (112 €/ha) and fine particulate matter formation (67 €/ha). These three categories together account for over 80% of total environmental costs, indicating that climate-related emissions, toxicity linked to feed production and handling, and air pollution are the main environmental pressure points of the system. Other relevant contributions arise from terrestrial acidification (7.3%) and marine eutrophication (5.4%), both closely linked to nutrient losses and feed-related emissions (Figure 35).

Figure 34. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the restoration practice implemented in the LH1

Figure 35. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH1 (accounting more than 99% of the total environmental costs)

Overall, the results indicate that the environmental performance of LH1 is largely determined by **animal-related processes**, especially feed production and associated emissions, suggesting that mitigation strategies targeting feed composition, sourcing, and livestock management could yield substantial reductions in total environmental costs.

When environmental costs are integrated in the economic assessment, the rotational grazing system implemented in LH1 shows a **negative economic balance**. Despite relatively low management costs (253 €/ha) and moderate revenues from livestock production (175 €/ha), the inclusion of environmental costs (354 €/ha) substantially affects the overall performance, resulting in a net balance of -432 €/ha. **Environmental costs account for 58% of total costs**, highlighting their significant weight in the economic assessment and the relevance of internalising environmental externalities when evaluating land management practices.

Table 9. e-CBA performance of LH1 Forest

LH1		Forest
Market	Revenues	175
	Costs	253
Non-market	Environmental costs	354.15
	Net ES benefits	17,389.88
Social Margin		17,137.73

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. **Social margin** = market margin + non-market margin

However, this result should be interpreted alongside the ecosystem services (ES) valuation reported in D3.2, which shows that the transition to rotational grazing leads to an overall improvement in the provision of regulating and cultural services compared to the initial forest management without livestock. Although these benefits are largely non-market and therefore not reflected in production revenues, they generate a positive net social value of +17,390 €/ha per year.

Taken together, these findings underline that, while rotational grazing may appear economically inefficient when assessed solely by-market outputs, **accounting** for both negative **externalities (environmental costs)** and positive externalities (**ecosystem service benefits**) is essential to capture its true societal performance and avoid misleading conclusions based only on private profitability.

These results highlight the role of regenerative grazing as a management option to restore soil functions while supporting economic activity in Mediterranean forestry systems.

LH6 – BOREAL FORESTRY SOIL (LATVIA) – EFFECT OF FERTILIZATION, SELECTION OF SPECIES, TREE BREEDING AND SUSTAINABLE SOIL MANAGEMENT

The main soil threats in this area include low below- and aboveground biodiversity, erosion, GHG emissions, low soil quality with risk of nutrient deficiency, low soil organic matter content, landscape simplification, soil acidity, and inappropriate groundwater levels.

Since 2001, the area representative of high soil health has been designated as a research territory, where sustainable management practices have been implemented to keep high soil health (Figure 36). These practices include nutrient balance management, reforestation to promote vegetation cover, tending to improve light conditions for specific species, and gentle soil preparation techniques

Figure 36. Photos of some different practices applied in the forestry soils of LH6

The results confirm that sustainable management practices applied in boreal forestry soils are associated with low **total environmental costs, amounting to around 80 €/ha**. (Figure 37).

These environmental costs are **mainly driven by recultivation activities**, which represent 46% of total, mainly related to machinery use, especially during soil preparation phase. Soil conditioning is the second most important contributor, accounting for 23% (19 €/ha). This impact is mainly linked to the use of soil pH correction materials, such as calcium carbonate, whose extraction and processing are energy intensive. **Planting activities also contributed noticeably** (15% of the total costs, 12 €/ha), reflecting the environmental burden associated with tree seeding production.

Figure 37. Environmental costs (€/ha) of the restoration practice implemented in the LH6

From an impact category perspective, environmental burden was dominated by GWP (34%) and FPM (32%), followed by human toxicity related impacts (together representing about 25% of total environmental costs) (Figure 38). These results are coherent with the LCA findings, which highlighted machinery use, soil conditioning materials and limited use of plant protection products as the main environmental hotspots.

Figure 38. Main impact categories contributing to the environmental costs of the intervention in the LH6

Table 10. e-CBA performance of LH6 Forest (€/ha/year)

LH6		Forest
Market	Revenues	0.00
	Costs	274.26
Non-market	Environmental costs	15.61
	Net ES benefits	490.86
Social Margin		200.99

(*) Results expressed in €/ha per year. **Social margin** = market margin + non-market margin

When environmental costs are integrated into the economic assessment, the **LH6 intervention shows a negative market balance** due to investment and management costs (274 €/ha per year) and the absence of current revenues from wood production (Table 10). It is expected that future timber sales could provide additional income, potentially improving private margins over time.

The monetised environmental costs were originally calculated at 80 €/ha, but a large part of these are associated with re-cultivation, planting and soil conditioning activities, which should be considered as long-term investments rather than annual operating costs. When annualised over a 20-year period (consistent with D3.2) a direct comparison with recurrent market costs and private margins is allowed, reinforcing the consistency of the e-CBA. Thus, the **annual equivalent environmental cost of 16 €/ha per year** indicates a **moderate environmental burden relative to economic effort**, being 5.5% of the total costs.

Despite the negative economic balance, the intervention generates substantial ecosystem service benefits, such as supporting services contributing most and a net increase in non-market value of **475 €/ha** compared to the abandoned area (based on the non-market valuation reported in D3.2). Overall, the **social margin of the restoration is positive (+201 €/ha per year)**, proving that, although economically unattractive from a market perspective, the intervention delivers a clear positive societal value.

5. Conclusions

The integration of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and environmental Cost-Benefit Analysis (e-CBA) within the InBestSoil project provides a robust framework to evaluate soil management. By translating environmental impacts associated with the restoration and alternative practices into a common monetary metric (€), this approach reveals "hidden" costs often ignored in traditional economic assessments.

The results of this analysis lead to several key conclusions:

- The study reveals that **environmental costs are a significant part of the real cost of land management, accounting for 20% to 60% of total costs** in several cases. Assessments based solely on private profitability may therefore be misleading. In some cases (e.g., conventional agricultural systems), practices that appear financially viable generate net social losses once environmental externalities are internalised. This directly supports the Soil Mission objective of making the value of soil health measurable and visible.
- Evidence from **agricultural** systems (e.g., LH7) shows that **switching to organic and regenerative practices can reduce environmental costs by 33%** while simultaneously improving socio-economic value. However, the analysis also identifies "hotspots," such as the intensive use of machinery in several biodynamic systems (e.g., LL2), suggesting that even sustainable practices must be optimised to reduce their operational footprint.
- In **urban** contexts (LH4, LH5), **sustainable practices** like grasslands or urban gardening show a strongly **positive net social benefit** due to their low environmental impact and high provision of ecosystem services, demonstrating the economic rationale for soil-based urban interventions.
- For severely degraded **industrial** and mining sites (LH2, LH3), the high initial financial and environmental costs of restoration using Technosols are justified as one-time capital investments. These costs are largely offset by the long-term recovery of vital ecosystem services, resulting in **strongly positive social outcomes**.
- In Mediterranean **forestry** (e.g., LH1), regenerative grazing shows that while these practices might have higher environmental costs due to livestock, they generate significant social value through improved soil health and biodiversity. This highlights that a **positive social margin often justifies practices that may seem less efficient from a purely market-based perspective**.
- The LCA–eCBA framework serves as a practical tool for identifying environmental "hotspots" and designing management systems that are both economically viable and ecologically resilient. These results provide a scientific basis for policymakers at the national and EU levels to design incentives, such as subsidies or regulations, that support the objectives of the EU Soil Mission.

In summary, the InBestSoil e-CBA framework establishes a methodological foundation for upscaling sustainability assessments. The results demonstrate that sustainable soil management is not only an environmental necessity but also a socio-economic strategy.

Using Euros (€) as a single metric allows policymakers to compare biophysical impacts with economic reality, making the value of natural capital visible.

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